

SUPPLY CHAIN SECURITY: ASSESSING CONFIDENCE IN FOOD DEFENSE COMPLIANCE AS A FUNCTION OF
MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS 4.0 DEPLOYMENT IN TRUCK TRANSPORTATION

by

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ABSTRACT

The secure transportation of food via trucks within the supply chain is a pivotal aspect of ensuring food safety and defense, necessitating the seamless integration of advanced security control processes and systems. This study primarily investigates how the integrated use of Industry 4.0 (4IR) technologies, such as AI, IoT, and Blockchain, alongside ISO standards like ISO 28001 and ISO 22000, in trucking management systems for food transport influences the confidence of supply chain professionals in ensuring that food products remain safe and untampered with during truck transportation.

To ensure the robustness of our survey, a two-round Delphi study involving 10 experts in supply chain management was conducted to validate the survey questions concerning truck security in food transportation. Following this validation, the survey was disseminated across several LinkedIn groups focused on food safety, food transportation, and supply chain management. A total of 55 responses were collected and analyzed. The analysis revealed that seal integrity was considered the most critical aspect of truck security, followed by concerns regarding cabin weight changes and cabin temperature. Conversely, the accuracy of driver records and the number of stops were deemed less significant. These insights facilitated the development of a confidence assessment model, where the confidence rating $C=a(LC)+b(IoT)+c(AI)+d(BC)+e(ISO)$, quantifies the impact of Legacy Controls (LC), Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Blockchain (BC), and ISO Standards (ISO) in enhancing the security of food transport.

The study's findings provide a foundational framework and a critical tool for supply chain professionals, empowering them to make informed decisions on security measures and compliance strategies, thereby ensuring food safety. It also contributes to advancing management practices, integrating industrial engineering principles with emerging technologies, and deepening our understanding of their practical application in food transportation security.

This work is dedicated to my children, Cynthia, Kevin, Alex, Britney, and Joseph, who have been a blessing in my life.

The work is also dedicated to all the children worldwide who will benefit from the improved management of food supply chains because of the transportation security, food safety, and food defense initiatives deployed based on Industry 4.0 technologies and management system standards such as those herein discussed.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

4IR	Fourth Industrial Revolution
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MS 4.0	Management Systems 4.0
SCM	Supply Chain Management

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Global supply chains, especially those involving the transportation of food via trucks, represent intricate and evolving systems that encompass numerous organizations and business partners. These chains are susceptible to disruptions and security threats that can negatively affect the economic vitality of nations and their global trading partners. The ability to prevent or swiftly detect security incidents within these truck transportation networks is crucial for averting crises and their potentially disastrous consequences. Such proactive measures safeguard individuals, food products, infrastructure, and transportation assets. Both the economy and society benefit significantly from enhancing the security and resilience of these essential supply chain components

Industrial engineering principles, such as process design, quality control, and risk assessment, are essential for ensuring the integrity of the food supply chain from the farm to the food table. However, the path from the farm to the food table requires the effective functioning of an ecosystem of humans, information, facilities, and equipment. The latter must be adequately operated, monitored, and maintained to ensure their integrity and proper food safety and defense, following industry best practices.

Supply chain professionals specifically engaged in the truck transportation of food face the crucial challenge of preventing tampering and adulteration of food products and ingredients during transit. The methods employed to assess confidence in these truck delivery systems can differ widely, influenced by the professionals' organizational context, business models, as well as their geographic location and role within the global food supply chain. This variability underscores the necessity for the development of management system models tailored to the truck transportation sector. Such models would enable supply chain professionals to quantitatively evaluate and categorize their confidence in the compliance and integrity of food shipments, ensuring adherence to food safety and defense standards.

The research in this paper aims to develop models that can be used by all stakeholders to ascertain if the security controls to ensure food safety are effective and meet regulatory compliance obligations. This is a function of the transportation companies' degree of implementation of Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools combined with applicable ISO management system standards. Hence, these models are herein referred to as Management System 4.0 (MS 4.0) models.

The MS 4.0 approaches presented in this paper are based on a combination of ISO standards such as ISO 28001 and ISO 22000. ISO 28001 is designed to help organizations establish a systematic approach to risk management that can help prevent and mitigate security threats to the supply chain. The standard includes requirements for conducting security assessments, developing security plans, and establishing procedures for monitoring and reviewing security performance. By implementing this standard, organizations can ensure that they have adequate security measures in place to protect their supply chain from potential security breaches, including those related to food defense.

On the other hand, ISO 22000 provides a framework for developing and implementing a food safety management system that can help prevent, reduce, or eliminate food safety hazards. The standard covers all aspects of the food chain from farm to table and includes requirements for developing and implementing food safety policies, conducting hazard analysis and risk assessments, establishing control measures, and monitoring and reviewing the effectiveness of food safety practices. By implementing this standard, organizations can ensure that they have an effective food safety program in place that can help prevent and mitigate food safety hazards, including those related to food defense.

Table 1 ISO Management System Standards for Security in the Food Supply Chain

Standard	Scope	Year of Publication
ISO 22000	"Food safety management systems — Requirements for any organization in the food chain."	2018
ISO 28001	"Security management systems for the supply chain — Best practices for implementing supply chain security, assessments, and plans — Requirements and guidance,"	2007

The combination of these two standards provides a comprehensive approach to food defense compliance that covers both the security and safety aspects of the food supply chain. By implementing these standards, organizations can ensure that they have a robust system in place for managing food defense risks and complying with regulatory requirements. The MS 4.0 models presented in this paper integrate the requirements of these two standards with 4IR tools to provide a holistic approach to supply chain security and food defense compliance, enabling supply chain professionals to make better-informed decisions that enhance the safety, quality, and security of the food supply chain.

Just as there are several standards that have been published by ISO that are not all applicable to supply-chain security, there are also a myriad of technologies that can be considered part of 4IR. For this reason, the selection of the best 4IR tools and emerging information technologies to support the practices suggested in the above standards is the foundational basis and approach adopted, which is consistent with Industrial Engineering principles based on Scientific Management.

Aligned with the goals outlined previously, this study focuses on the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and Blockchain as three pivotal 4IR technologies that underpin the MS 4.0 models for enhancing the security and safety of food transportation via trucks. AI's capability to sift through and analyze extensive data sets enables the identification of patterns and

anomalies potentially indicative of security threats or food safety risks within trucking logistics. Meanwhile, IoT devices offer the advantage of monitoring and tracking food products throughout the truck transportation process, ensuring real-time insights into crucial factors like location, temperature, and other conditions impacting product quality and safety. Blockchain technology contributes by establishing a secure, transparent ledger of all supply chain transactions and interactions, thus providing a tamper-proof and auditable history of all activities pertinent to food safety and defense during truck transport.

Employing these cutting-edge information technologies, grounded in Industrial Engineering principles through the MS 4.0 framework discussed in this dissertation, is anticipated to empower all supply chain stakeholders. It aims to facilitate more informed, risk-based decisions concerning the security and integrity of food products during their journey across global supply chains, specifically focusing on the truck transportation segment.

Table 2 4IR Tools Utilized in Connection with MS 4.0

4IR Tool	Description	Benefit to Supply Chains
Internet of Things (IoT)	Devices connected to the internet to collect and exchange data	Real-time monitoring and tracking of food shipments
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Computer systems performing tasks that would typically require human intelligence	Enhanced prediction and mitigation of potential risks in the food supply chain
Blockchain	A distributed ledger that records transactions across multiple computers	Increased transparency and traceability of food shipments

Other common technologies associated with Industry 4.0 include Robotics, Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Additive Manufacturing, and Cyber-Physical Systems (Salesforce, 2019)(i-scoop.eu, n.d.) It is important to note that Cloud Technology is not highlighted in this research paper given that at the time of this writing it has become a common information technology for infrastructure (MachineMetrics, n.d.). Additionally, other technologies, such as Big Data and Cybersecurity are important considerations that would need to be addressed (MachineMetrics, n.d.) in conjunction with the specific technologies being studied in this paper, will be subject of future research.

It is evident that a significant advantage of utilizing MS 4.0 within the truck transportation segment of the food supply chain lies in its capacity to bolster transparency. This is achieved by establishing a secure and transparent log of all transactions and interactions related to the transportation of food products, fostering trust among stakeholders and facilitating adherence to regulatory standards. Additionally, this research explores the broader implications of applying MS 4.0. These approaches empower supply chain professionals, particularly those involved in trucking logistics, with the necessary insights to make more informed decisions. Such decisions are aimed at improving the overall safety, quality, and security of the food products during their journey across the supply chain, ensuring that food reaches consumers safely and without compromise. The models developed in this research could be adapted for use in other industries, such as pharmaceuticals, where the transportation of goods is critical to the delivery of essential products to consumers.

Table 3 Benefits of MS 4.0-Based Approaches for Supply Chain Stakeholders

Benefit	Description	Associated 4IR Technology
Enhanced Risk Management	Making better risk-based choices regarding the security of global supply chains	AI, IoT, Blockchain
Real-Time Visibility	Access to real-time information about location, temperature, and other environmental conditions	IoT
Improved Decision Making	Informed decisions based on data patterns and trends identified through AI	AI
Increased Transparency	Providing a secure and transparent record of all transactions and interactions in the supply chain, which helps build trust among stakeholders and ensures compliance with regulations	Blockchain

In general, the development of MS 4.0 models that consider 4IR tools and ISO management system standards via the application of sound Industrial Engineering principles is expected to help all stakeholders in making better risk-based choices regarding security in global supply chains.

Background and Environment

The global food supply chain is a complex network of interconnected entities, from the farm to the table, and its importance has become increasingly evident over the last few decades (Focker & van der Fels-Klerx, 2019). The food supply chain includes primary production, processing, manufacturing, distribution, and retailing. As a result of its complexity, the food supply chain is vulnerable to a variety of risks, including food safety risks, food fraud, and food defense risks. Food defense is defined as the protection of food products from intentional contamination or adulteration, which could cause harm to consumers, disrupt the food supply chain, and damage the economy. ("Food Defense," n.d.)

Industry 4.0 or The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) is described as "a technological revolution that will fundamentally alter the way we live, work, and relate to one another" (Schwab, 2016, para. 1). According to Kagermann et al. (2013), the Fourth Industrial Revolution is characterized by "a range of new technologies that are fusing the physical, digital, and biological worlds" (p. 6). Lasi et al. (2014) explain that Industry 4.0 is "about more than just technology-driven change" and presents an opportunity for everyone to create an inclusive, human-centered future (p. 240).

4IR, such as blockchain, artificial intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT), have shown the potential to enhance the security and transparency of the food supply chain (Fernandez-Carames & Fraga-Lamas, 2018). Blockchain technology provides a secure and transparent record of all transactions and interactions in the supply chain, providing an immutable and auditable trail of all activities related to food safety and defense (Khan et al., 2022) AI can be used to analyze large volumes of data and identify patterns and anomalies that may indicate security threats (Zeng, Cao, & Neill, 2021) or food safety risks. IoT devices can be used to monitor and track products throughout the supply chain, providing real-time visibility into the location, temperature, and other environmental conditions that can affect product quality and safety (Kumar et al., 2022).

Another consideration is that the globalization of food production and distribution has increased the complexity of the food supply chain, making it more vulnerable to food defense risks (Mitenius, Kennedy, & Busta, 2013). Food defense risks are intentional actions that aim to cause harm to the food supply chain, disrupt food production and distribution, and cause harm to consumers (FDA, 2019). The added geographical complexity of the food supply chain has made it an attractive target for terrorists and other malicious actors, who can exploit the vulnerabilities in the supply chain to cause harm to the public and damage the economy.

The consequences of a food defense incident can be severe, ranging from damage to public health to economic losses. In the event of a food defense incident, the impact on the public's health can be significant, depending on the severity of the incident (CDC, 2019). Consumers can suffer from health problems or even death as a result of consuming contaminated food (Nordhagen et al., 2022), while the economic impact can result in losses of billions of dollars. It is essential to mitigate the risk of food defense incidents by taking a proactive approach to food defense, which includes measures such as implementing food defense plans, increasing awareness and training of employees, and enhancing physical security (Department of Homeland Security, 2021).

Given the above, it is evident that Food defense is a critical issue for the food industry and government agencies responsible for regulating the food supply chain. The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has developed a food defense plan that outlines the steps that food facilities can take to protect their products from intentional contamination or adulteration. The FDA's food defense plan includes measures such as conducting vulnerability assessments, implementing mitigation strategies, and developing an emergency response plan.

Another measure being taken by food regulatory bodies to prevent food defense incidents is the implementation of the Food Safety Modernization Act (FSMA), which requires food facilities to develop and implement food defense plans (FDA, 2019). The FSMA requires food facilities to conduct vulnerability assessments, identify and implement mitigation strategies, and develop food defense plans that are updated regularly. FSMA is being supported by some of the 4IR technologies herein mentioned, such as blockchain and the Internet of Things (IoT), in order to enhance food traceability and transparency in the supply chain (Kaur et al., 2022). These technologies support FSMA as they provide a secure and transparent record of all transactions and interactions in the supply chain, which can help prevent food fraud and improve food safety and defense.

In recent years all of the above approaches are starting to be deployed in the transport of food. In particular, there has been a growing interest in using Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools to enhance the safety and security of food products during transport. Once again it is Industry 4.0 tools, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain technology (Singh et al., 2023), and artificial intelligence (AI), that are being used to mitigate the risks associated with food defense by providing real-time monitoring and tracking of food products during transport. These tools can also help supply chain professionals identify potential security breaches and take corrective action before they become major incidents.

Although there are other technologies associated with Industry 4.0, such as robotics, augmented reality, virtual reality, additive manufacturing, and cyber-physical systems, these technologies are outside of the scope of this paper. It's worth mentioning that cloud technology is not highlighted in the research since it is more of an infrastructure technology that is already broadly used (Salesforce, 2019) (MachineMetrics, n.d.). Additionally, big data and cybersecurity concerns are important considerations that need to be addressed in conjunction with the specific technologies (MachineMetrics, n.d.) such as those being considered in this paper, and can be the subject of future research.

The use of Industry 4.0 tools in the food supply chain is still in its infancy, and there is a need for research to explore the potential benefits and challenges associated with using these tools. This paper aims to contribute to this research by developing Management System 4.0 models that supply chain professionals can use to quantify and classify the confidence that they should have in the food shipments they receive meeting their compliance obligations pertaining to food safety and defense as a function of the transportation companies' degree of implementation of Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools combined with applicable ISO management system standards.

Problem Statement

The potential impact of a food defense incident on public health and the economy can be significant. In the event of a food defense incident, the impact on the public's health can be severe, depending on the severity of the incident. The economic impact of food defense incidents can result in losses of billions of dollars. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) estimates that foodborne illnesses cost the U.S. economy \$15.6 billion annually, with most of the costs being borne by the food industry (FDA, 2019). Such incidents can result in significant damage to a country's economy and reputation (Abideen et al., 2021)

The deployment of Industry 4.0 (4IR) technologies, including the Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain, and artificial intelligence (AI), offers promising avenues to address food defense risks, particularly through real-time monitoring and tracking of food products during their transport via trucks. Nevertheless, there exists a critical need for research to delve into the advantages and challenges linked with these advanced tools. Such research should aim to create Management System 4.0 (MS 4.0) frameworks. These frameworks would enable supply chain professionals, especially those focusing on truck transportation, to effectively measure and categorize their confidence in the compliance and integrity of food shipments they manage. This confidence assessment is crucial, considering the transportation companies' extent of 4IR technology adoption in tandem with relevant ISO management system standards for food safety and defense.

At present, apart from conducting their own inspections and audits, supply chain professionals lack a validated methodology to gauge the implementation level of 4IR technologies and ISO standards-based controls employed by trucking companies to prevent the adulteration of food during its transport. This gap underscores the importance of developing robust MS 4.0 models to provide a structured approach for evaluating the security and safety measures in place for food transportation.

Potential Solution

The potential solution to the problem of food defense in the food supply chain is the use of Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain technology, and artificial intelligence (AI), to enhance the safety and security of food products during transport. These tools can provide real-time monitoring and tracking of food products during transport via trucks, as well as identify potential security breaches and take corrective action before they become major incidents.

In addition to real-time monitoring and tracking, AI, IoT, and Blockchain can bring other benefits to the food industry in terms of food safety and defense. For example, AI can be used for food quality control, predicting food spoilage, and monitoring food contamination in processing plants (Bhat et al., 2022). IoT devices can also be used to ensure food quality and safety by detecting and reporting deviations from acceptable temperature, humidity, and light conditions during transport and storage (Sharma et al., 2020). Furthermore, Blockchain can also be used to prevent food fraud and improve traceability in the supply chain by providing a secure and transparent record of all transactions and interactions (Chandan et al., 2023).

The development of Management System 4.0 models that supply chain professionals can use to quantify and classify the confidence that they should have in the food shipments they receive meeting their compliance obligations pertaining to food safety and defense as a function of the transportation companies' degree of implementation of Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools combined with applicable ISO management system standards is another potential solution to the problem of food defense in the food supply chain. These models can help supply chain professionals make better risk-based choices regarding the security of those global supply chains.

Research Objectives

In accordance with the purpose of this research, the following objectives have been identified:

1. To conduct a thorough literature review on the topics of food defense, Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools, and ISO standards related to food safety and defense.
2. To study the specific security concerns that supply chain executives have regarding the transport of food via trucks, and understand the relative importance of those concerns pertaining to the safety, quality, and security of food products.
3. To develop Management System 4.0 models that supply chain professionals overseeing truck transportation in the food supply chain can use to quantify and classify the confidence that they should have in that food shipments are safe and in compliance with food safety and defense regulations, as a function of the transportation companies' degree of implementation of Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools, combined with applicable ISO management system standards.
4. To compare the results of this study to previous studies and highlight the implications for practice and future research.

Potential Contributions to the Body of Knowledge

The potential contributions of this study to the Industrial Engineering body of knowledge include:

1. A better understanding of the concerns associated with the safe and secure transport of food via trucks and how these are monitored using Industry 4.0 (4IR) technologies.

2. The development of MS 4.0 models aimed at empowering supply chain professionals to effectively measure and categorize their confidence levels in the compliance of food transported via trucks. This evaluation is a function of the extent to which trucking companies have adopted Industry 4.0 technologies alongside relevant ISO management system standards to ensure food safety and defense.

3. A better understanding of the limitations and opportunities associated with employing Industry 4.0 (4IR) technologies and ISO management system standards in securing the truck transportation of food within the supply chain.

Outline of the Dissertation

This dissertation will be organized into five chapters, as follows:

Chapter 1: Introduction - This chapter provides an overview of the problem of food defense in the food supply chain and the potential solutions that can be implemented to enhance the safety and security of food products during truck transport. It outlines the research objectives, potential contributions to the body of knowledge, and provides this detailed outline of the content of the dissertation.

Chapter 2: Literature Review - This chapter reviews the literature on food defense, Industry 4.0 (4IR) tools, and ISO management system standards related to food safety and defense. It provides a critical analysis of the current state of the art and identifies gaps in the literature that this study aims to address.

Chapter 3: Methodology - This chapter describes the methodology used in this study, including the methods for empirical data collection for the development of the Management System 4.0 models, applicable to the secure transport of food via trucks.

Chapter 4: Findings - This chapter presents the study's findings and their implications, including a summary of the key findings, the theoretical and practical implications of the findings, and the limitations of the study.

Chapter Five: Conclusion - This chapter provides a summary of the study's main findings, their implications, and recommendations for future research. It discusses the study's contributions to the body of knowledge on food defense and the use of Industry 4.0 tools and ISO management system standards in the food supply chain.

Summary of Chapter 1

This chapter has provided an overview of the problem of food defense in the food supply chain and the importance of using Industry 4.0 tools and ISO management system standards to enhance the safety and security of food products during transport via trucks. It has also outlined the research objectives, potential contributions to the body of knowledge, and the outline of the dissertation.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

Abstract

This literature review examined the interplay between Industry 4.0 tools and ISO management system standards in enhancing supply chain security for food safety and food defense compliance. The study delves into current research on this topic, investigating how integrating Industry 4.0 tools and technologies with ISO management system standards impacts food safety during transportation and ensures adherence to food defense regulations.

Further, it assessed how the amalgamation of these tools and standards influences the confidence of supply chain professionals in maintaining transportation security and food safety. By synthesizing available evidence, this review identified critical themes and trends in the literature and offers an overview of the prevailing research landscape. It also highlights gaps in the evidence base that warrant further investigation.

Ultimately, this review contributed to a deeper understanding of the role of Industry 4.0 and ISO management system standards in bolstering food safety and defense, paving the way for future research and practice in this critical area.

Introduction

Food safety and food defense are critical aspects of the food industry, and supply chain security plays a significant role in ensuring both. In recent years, introducing Industry 4.0 has presented new opportunities for enhancing supply chain security and, consequently, food safety and defense compliance.

Herein referred to as “Management Systems 4.0”, the application of Industry 4.0 combined with ISO standards comprises an interconnected system that integrates the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence and blockchain to create a more efficient and effective supply chain.

This literature review explored the effectiveness of Management Systems 4.0 in strengthening supply chain security for food safety and food defense compliance. This was done by synthesizing the available evidence; this review seeks to identify key themes and trends in the literature, provide an overview of the current state of research, and highlight gaps in the evidence base that warrant further investigation.

Finally, the review contributed to a better understanding of Management Systems 4.0 in enhancing food safety and food defense and inform future research and practice in this area.

Review Methodology

The method used for conducting this literature review is outlined and discussed below:

Development of the research questions

The first critical step in this comprehensive literature review was formulating research questions. These questions were created to thoroughly explore the current knowledge regarding integrating Industry 4.0 tools and ISO standards, their impact on supply chain professionals' confidence, and the strengths and limitations of existing evidence.

Identifying knowledge gaps and understanding how the combined application of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards enhances supply chain security and food safety was vital.

Specifically, this review addressed the following research questions:

- What is the current literature on using Industry 4.0 and ISO management system standards to improve supply chain security for food safety and defense compliance?
- How does integrating Industry 4.0 tools and technologies with ISO management system standards improve food safety during transportation and facilitate compliance with food defense regulations?
- How does the combined application of Industry 4.0 tools and techniques with ISO management system standards such as ISO 28001 and ISO 22000 affect the confidence of supply chain professionals regarding transportation security and food safety?

This review was conducted to deepen the understanding of Industry 4.0 and ISO Management Systems standards in advancing food safety and food defense by answering these questions. In turn, the review provides recommendations for future research and practice in this area, helping to ensure a secure and safe food supply chain that protects consumer health and well-being. Additionally, this analysis will help to steer future studies and inform decision-making in food safety and supply chain management by evaluating the evidence base's implications.

Addressing these questions will contribute to devising more effective strategies for ensuring food safety and compliance with food defense regulations across the supply chain. The outcome of this research, via an effective review, benefits the industry and consumers by establishing a foundation for informed decisions and strategic enhancements in food safety and supply chain management by focusing on these areas.

Definition of inclusion and exclusion criteria

The searches carried out focused on review articles and research articles. The exclusion criteria for the review included articles not published in English, those that did not specifically address AI, Blockchain, IoT, or ISO standards for ensuring transport security and food safety, and articles published in 2022 and 2023. The initial criteria are that any article not covering Food Defense, Industry 4.0, and either ISO 22000 or ISO 28001 would be discarded. If that does not yield good sources, the criteria would be adjusted to exclude those that did not address Food Defense and/or Industry 4.0, ISO 22000, or ISO 28001.

These criteria helped filter out irrelevant or outdated research that was not considered to contribute to the current understanding of the topic. The systematic review maintained a focused approach by adhering to these inclusion and exclusion criteria, yielding a comprehensive and up-to-date analysis of the relevant literature that addresses the three research questions.

Search for the publications

Mind Mapping

According to Buzan (2008), a mind map is an image-centered diagram visually representing connections between hierarchically different components of learned material. This organizational tool helps individuals brainstorm, plan, and understand complex ideas by displaying them as interconnected branches stemming from a central concept. Further, mind maps enable the researcher to see the relationships between various aspects of a topic, facilitating better comprehension and retention of information. Below is a mind map centered created around Food Safety Confidence:

Figure 1 Mind Map

With the above diagram, there is a better appreciation of how each of the Industry 4.0 and ISO standard subject matter elements of this paper come together to provide confidence that food will be safe for consumption. Also, the map depicts how AI can complement human decisions regarding transportation and food safety controls. The map shows how Blockchain can be used to ensure that records are reliable in support of Food Defense compliance. It also shows how Cloud and IoT technologies can monitor transportation conditions to prevent or detect adulteration and other non-desirable process conditions.

In the context of this literature review, the mind map helped search for publications as it provided a visual overview of the main themes and concepts related to the research topic in this paper.

Database Search

Two academic databases were utilized to gather relevant publications to ensure a comprehensive and systematic literature review. Web of Science and Science Direct were chosen for their extensive coverage of scholarly publications and wide range of sources for evaluation. This approach ensured that the literature review was not biased towards any specific geographic location and that a broad range of relevant sources was considered.

Boolean operators were developed to search the databases thoroughly and efficiently to identify relevant literature for the research questions. These operators were derived from the previously presented mind map, illustrating the connections between various technologies, standards, and their impacts on food safety confidence. The mind map showed that transportation controls, secure transportation, and effective monitoring were linked to artificial intelligence, ISO 28001 compliance, IoT, and cloud technology on the left side. On the right side, food defense compliance was connected to blockchain technology, ISO 22000 compliance, and food safety controls. All these components contributed to developing search criteria entered into Web of Science and science direct databases in boolean format. The boolean search operations employed are shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4 Searches and Criteria

Search #	Criteria
1	(AI OR BLOCKCHAIN OR IoT OR "ISO 22000" OR "ISO 28001)
2	((FOOD SAFETY) AND (TRANSPORT) AND ("INDUSTRY 4.0" OR "AI" OR BLOCKCHAIN OR "IOT" OR (INTERNET OF THINGS)))
3	("ISO 28001" OR "ISO28001") AND "Food Defense"
4	("ISO 22000" OR "ISO22000") AND "Food Defense"
5	(IoT OR "Internet of Things") AND ("Food Transportation" OR "Food Logistics" OR "Food Supply Chain" AND "Food Safety")
6	("ISO 28000") AND ("Industry 4.0")
7	("ISO 22000") AND ("Industry 4.0")

As mentioned, only open-access articles published between 2022 and 2023 were included in the search to ensure relevance and accuracy. This decision was based on the latest advancements and discussions in food safety, Industry 4.0 technologies, and ISO management systems standards. This rigorous search strategy, grounded in the relationships and connections illustrated by the mind map and further refined by focusing on specific publication years, open-access articles, and relevant research areas, provided a solid foundation for a comprehensive and insightful examination of food defense compliance, Industry 4.0 technologies, and ISO management systems standards in the context of food transport.

Between the two databases, a total of fourteen (14) searches were conducted, considering the seven (7) different boolean search criteria for each of the two (2) databases, Web of Science and Science Direct. The resulting articles were screened for relevance, and the table below summarizes the results of the fourteen (14) searches:

Table 5 Results of Boolean Searches

Search #	Boolean Search Criteria	Web of Science Results	Relevant Web of Science Results	ScienceDirect Results	Relevant ScienceDirect Results	Total Results	Relevant Total Results
1	(AI OR BLOCKCHAIN OR IoT OR "ISO 22000" OR "ISO 28001")	27	2	3	2	30	4
2	TS=((FOOD SAFETY) AND (TRANSPORT) AND ("INDUSTRY 4.0" OR "AI" OR BLOCKCHAIN OR "IOT" OR (INTERNET OF THINGS)))	2	2	82	5	84	7
3	("ISO 28001" OR "ISO28001") AND "Food Defense"	0	0	1	1	1	1
4	("ISO 22000" OR "ISO22000") AND "Food Defense"	0	0	1	1	1	1
5	(IoT OR "Internet of Things") AND ("Food Transportation" OR "Food Logistics" OR "Food Supply Chain" AND "Food Safety")	24	16	158	15	182	31
6	("ISO 28000") AND ("Industry 4.0")	0	0	1	1	1	1
7	("ISO 22000") AND ("Industry 4.0")	1	1	6	2	7	3
Total		54	21	253	27	307	48

Selection of the studies

The searches yielded three hundred and seven (307) publications (see table above), and a preliminary screening process identified a total of forty (48) publications that met the criteria for further analysis. Four (4) of the twentyone (21) Web of Science publications were discarded due to replication, leaving seventeen (17) publications.

After another round of filtering, another set of publications was discarded because they needed to address food defense or Industry 4.0, leaving only nine Web of Science publications for further analysis. Similarly, of the Twenty-Seven (27) ScienceDirect publications, Thirteen (13) were discarded due to a lack of relevance to Food Defense. This left Fourteen (14) ScienceDirect publications, of which eight

were found to have no relevance to Industry 4.0. As a result, only six (6) ScienceDirect publications remained for further analysis. See Table 6 for a simplified view of the screening process.

Table 6 The Screening Process

Number of Publications	Screening Process
307	Initial search yielded 307 publications
48	48 publications met criteria for further analysis
17	4 of 21 Web of Science publications discarded
9	9 Web of Science publications remained for analysis
14	13 of 27 ScienceDirect publications discarded
6	8 of 14 ScienceDirect publications discarded
15	9 Web of Science + 6 ScienceDirect publications studied

The rigorous screening process allowed a thorough analysis of the most relevant publications on Food Defense and Industry 4.0. By focusing on the publications directly related to the intersection of these two (2) fields, the analysis can provide valuable insights into how Industry 4.0 can be utilized to improve Food Defense. The table further details how the refinement process was employed using the mentioned criteria.

Table 7 Application of the Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Database	Total Publications Identified	Discarded due to Replication	Discarded due to Lack of Relevance	Discarded due to not Addressing Food Defense or Industry 4.0	Publications for Further Analysis
Web of Science	21	4	8	0	9
ScienceDirect	27	0	0	8	6
Total	48	4	8	8	15

As can be seen in Table 7, the nine (9) Web of Science publications and six (6) ScienceDirect publications that remained after filtering yielded fifteen (15) publications that can be studied in order to gain a comprehensive look at the current state of research on this topic.

Extracted data

Relevant data pertaining to the research questions were extracted from the selected studies and were summarized in the table below:

Table 8 Extracted Data for Final List of Included Publications

Publication	Authors	AI	IoT	Blockchain	Food Defense	ISO 22000	ISO 28001	Score
1	(Yadav et al., 2022)	1	1	1	1	1	0	5
2	(Wei et al., 2023)	1	1	1	1	0	0	4
3	(Mehannaoui et al., 2023)	0	1	0	1	1	0	3
4	(Tripathi et al., 2023)	0	1	1	1	0	0	3
5	(Tsoukas et al., 2022)	0	0	1	1	1	0	3
6	(Hameed et al., 2022)	0	1	1	1	0	0	3
7	(Ramanathan et al., 2022)	0	1	0	1	1	0	3
8	(Ehsan et al., 2022)	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
9	(Hassoun et al., 2023)	1	1	1	1	1	0	5
10	(Lu et al., 2022)	0	1	1	1	0	0	3
11	(Burgess et al., 2022)	1	0	1	1	1	1	5
12	(Khan et al., 2023)	0	1	0	1	1	1	4
13	(Patel et al., 2022)	0	0	1	1	1	1	4
14	(Nagarajan et al., 2022)	0	1	0	1	1	1	4
15	(Powell et al., 2022)	0	1	1	1	0	0	3

The above table depicts the scores of the fifteen (15) publications based on specific topics pertaining to the research questions: AI, IoT, Blockchain, Food Defense, ISO 22000, and ISO 28001. As mentioned earlier, the scores range from 2 to 5, with a higher score indicating a more substantial presence of the topics. Based on the data, publications 1, 9, and 11 scored the highest, with a score of 5, indicating a prominent presence of AI, IoT, Blockchain, Food Defense, and ISO 22000. These publications are recommended for researchers seeking comprehensive studies on these topics and were critical to the research of this paper.

On the other hand, publications 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 12, 13, 14, and 15 have scores ranging from 2 to 4, indicating a comparatively weaker presence of the topics. Although they scored low, they may still help understand a specific topic or combination of topics. For instance, publication 12 has a score of 4, indicating a strong presence of IoT, Blockchain, Food Defense, and ISO 22000 which, although it does not mention ISO 28001, may still be a solid article with valuable insights into the overall research questions. This publication is particularly relevant to those interested in these specific topics. The table offers a valuable overview of various topics in various publications, providing a helpful resource to prioritize reading the 15 publications.

Analysis and Discussion of the Findings

In analyzing the 15 publications, Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards can play a vital role in ensuring the safety and security of food during transportation, thereby increasing the confidence of supply chain stakeholders. Below is a discussion based on this deeper literature analysis in the context of the research questions.

Current State of the Literature

Yadav et al. (2022) summarized the recent developments of six technologies, including IoT and Blockchain, in the agriculture and food supply chain (AFSC). They concluded that these technologies could improve the efficiency and transparency of the supply chain and ensure food safety and security. Wei et al. (2023) proposed an IoT-based food supply chain management system that utilizes a Tree-Augmented Naive Bayes with PSO algorithm. The system can monitor and control the food supply chain in real-time, ensuring the safety and security of the food.

Mehannaoui et al. (2023) proposed a new definition for food traceability and architecture for IoT-based food traceability systems. They also classified the technologies used in this context. Tripathi et al. (2023) proposed a novel BIOT-based layered framework using EOSIO for effective food traceability and evaluated its performance. These studies show that Industry 4.0 technologies, such as IoT and Blockchain, can improve food traceability, an essential aspect of food safety.

ISO Management System Standards

ISO management system standards, such as ISO 22000 and ISO 28001, provide food safety and supply chain security guidelines. Tsoukas et al. (2022) proposed an end-to-end approach that uses blockchain technology, a self-sovereign identity approach, and TinyML to enhance the security of the food supply chain and increase the trustfulness of the food industry. They also discussed how ISO management system standards could improve the security of the food supply chain.

Hameed et al. (2022) presented a trusted, self-organized, traceable formal system based on Blockchain and IoT for modeling the food supply chain management system. They used smart contracts to automate payment procedures. Patel et al. (2022) proposed a blockchain-based supply chain management software to improve food safety, quality, and traceability throughout the agricultural supply chain. These studies suggest that combining Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards can improve the traceability and transparency of the food supply chain, which is essential for ensuring food safety and security.

Confidence of Supply Chain Professionals

Hassoun et al. (2023) reviewed the application of Traceability 4.0 in the fruits and vegetables sector, focusing on relevant Industry 4.0 enablers such as Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things, Blockchain, and Big Data. Lu et al. (2022) proposed a food anti-counterfeiting traceability system based on Blockchain and the Internet of Things to ensure the uniqueness of food and the authenticity and

reliability of the source data of the Blockchain. These studies show that Industry 4.0 technologies can increase the confidence of supply chain professionals regarding transportation security and food safety.

Khan et al. (2023) explored the barriers that hinder IoT adoption in the food supply chain. They identified a need for more awareness, uncertainty about return on investment, and lack of interoperability among the barriers. Nagarajan et al. (2022) proposed an IoT-based dynamic food supply chain for smart cities that provides intelligent vehicle routing and traces sources of contamination in FCM. Powell et al. (2022) reported observations and learnings from an ongoing beef supply chain project.

It is clear from this analysis of the literature that the implementing of Industry 4.0 technologies, such as IoT, AI, and Blockchain, along with compliance with food safety and security regulations via the implementation of ISO 22000 and ISO 28001, can enhance food defense measures during transportation and increase stakeholder confidence in the safety and quality of food products.

The literature affirms that these technologies can improve the traceability, transparency, and security of the supply chain while reducing the risk of errors and contamination. The use of these technologies and standards for compliance with regulations should be a priority for food industry stakeholders seeking to improve food safety and security and food defense compliance during transportation.

Finally, the literature makes it evident that there are still obstacles to be overcome before these technologies can be sufficiently implemented in the food supply chain to boost stakeholders' confidence. This indicates the need for additional research and study to overcome these problems and further develop and address the subject.

Need for Further Research (Gap)

The analysis conducted in the previous section revealed that adopting Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards has the potential to increase confidence in the safety and compliance of transported food products. Nonetheless, there needs to be more research related to developing models that can quantify the association between these technologies and standards and the confidence supply chain stakeholders have in the safety and compliance of transported food.

Further, Industry 4.0 technologies such as IoT, AI, and Blockchain can enable real-time monitoring and tracking of food products during transportation. This level of visibility can increase transparency in the supply chain and allow for early detection of any issues or potential hazards, leading to quicker and more effective corrective action. Integrating these technologies with ISO management system standards such as ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 can provide a framework for implementing food safety and defense measures throughout the supply chain.

Even though these technologies and standards have potential benefits, there needs to be more research on how they impact supply chain stakeholders' confidence in the safety and compliance of transported food. It is due to this gap in the research which highlights the need for the development of models that can quantify the association between the use of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards and the level of confidence that supply chain stakeholders have in the safety and compliance of transported food.

One potential approach to developing these models is using surveys and questionnaires to assess the perceptions of supply chain stakeholders regarding the use of these technologies and standards. Using these surveys, they can include questions about the perceived effectiveness of these technologies and standards in ensuring the safety and compliance of transported food. The surveys can

also consider the level of confidence that supply chain stakeholders have in implementing these technologies and standards throughout the supply chain.

The development of models that can associate the use of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards with the level of confidence that supply chain stakeholders have in the safety and compliance of transported food is essential for improving food safety and defense practices throughout the supply chain. This analysis can include factors such as the number of incidents, the severity of incidents, and the speed and effectiveness of the response to these incidents. These models can enable more informed decision-making regarding adopting these technologies and standards and help supply chain stakeholders identify areas for improvement. By closing the gap in research, it will be possible to develop more effective strategies that can ensure the safety of transported food products.

Chapter 2 Summary

This literature review examined the interplay between Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards for improving security of the supply chain for ensuring safe delivery of food. Over three hundred publications were found via boolean searches on Web of Science and Science Direct, of which upon applying the inclusion criteria, fifteen were deemed to be fully relevant to the scope of the research. In reading through the pertinent publications, the literature suggests that there are still obstacles to be overcome before these technologies can be sufficiently implemented in the food supply chain to boost stakeholders' confidence. Further research is needed to understand the association between these technologies and standards and the confidence supply chain stakeholders have in the safety and compliance of transported food.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

Introduction

As stressed in previous chapters, safety, and security are critical concerns in the food supply chain due to the potential for foodborne illnesses and intentional contamination. While progress has been made in improving food safety and security, there still needs to be better solutions, especially in transportation and logistics, due to the complexity of the food industry. A formal research methodology is crucial to ensure the reliability and validity of the study's findings.

The potential impact of this study lies in its ability to offer new insights and strategies for improving food safety and security in the food supply chain by integrating Industry 4.0 tools and technologies with ISO management system standards. The findings could contribute to the development of new policies, standards, and practices that ultimately benefit public health. By following the appropriate research methodology, the study findings can be trusted by the broader scientific community and help advance research in the field.

Overview of the Research Methodology

A well-defined research methodology provides a structured approach to gathering and analyzing data, enhancing the credibility of the study's conclusions. Establishing a sound research methodology regarding the confidence the Supply Chain professionals have in applying Industry 4.0 technologies for Food Defense can offer new insights and strategies to address the complex challenges the food industry faces, ultimately benefiting all food supply chain stakeholders.

Figure 2 below depicts an overview of the research methodology deployed for this study.

Figure 2 Research Methodology Flow Diagram

Original Idea and Scope Reduction

This stage of the methodology aims to ensure the clarity and viability of the research idea. Initially, the study aimed to investigate the application of Industry 4.0 and ISO management system standards across the entire food supply chain to improve food safety and defense compliance. However, due to the complexity and vastness of the food supply chain, the research was narrowed to focus solely on transportation via trucks.

The research now centers on studying security concerns and food defense vulnerabilities in the truck transportation system and assessing how the application of Industry 4.0 tools and technologies with ISO management system standards can enhance confidence of supply chain professionals.

Literature Review

The next stage in the methodology is the literature review. A formal literature review was conducted to establish a baseline understanding of the relationship between Industry 4.0 tools and ISO management system standards in enhancing supply chain security for food safety and food defense compliance. The review investigated the impact of integrating Industry 4.0 tools and technologies with ISO management system standards on food safety during transportation and adherence to food defense regulations, as well as the influence on the confidence of supply chain professionals in maintaining transportation security and food safety. The review synthesized available evidence to identify key themes and trends in the literature. It contributed to a deeper understanding of the role of Industry 4.0 and ISO management system standards in bolstering food safety and defense. Additionally, the review highlighted gaps in the evidence base that warrant further investigation, providing a foundation for the research methodology employed in this study.

Identification of Research Gap

The literature review (Chapter 2) identified the research gap to be addressed by the research which is the object of this paper. The gap reflects the need for more comprehensive research on the correlation between Industry 4.0 technologies, ISO management system standards, and the confidence of supply chain stakeholders in the safety and compliance of transported food. There is a need to establish this correlation due to the increasing demand for transparency and accountability in the food supply chain and the growing complexity of modern supply chains.

This paper describes the research methodology used to address this gap, which involves using surveys and questionnaires to assess supply chain stakeholders' perceptions of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards' effectiveness in ensuring the safety and compliance of transported food. The research also suggests further studies analyzing historical data on the safety and

compliance of transported food products to develop models predicting the level of confidence in the safety and compliance of transported food based on adopting these technologies and standards.

Integrating Industry 4.0 technologies with ISO management system standards and using a robust research methodology will provide a framework for implementing food safety and defense measures throughout the supply chain, benefiting public health worldwide.

Identification of Vulnerabilities in the Food Supply Chain

At this stage of the methodology, the vulnerabilities or security concerns associated with the transport of food were identified via the following means:

ISO Standards for Food Supply Chain Management

ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 serve as benchmark frameworks for identifying vulnerabilities in the supply chain related to food safety and supply chain security, mainly via the audit process. By using these standards as a guide, organizations can effectively identify areas of weakness, implement corrective actions, and continuously monitor the supply chain to ensure ongoing compliance and improvement and was a crucial element in identifying the security concerns used, and further details in this study.

Vulnerabilities Identified from Literature Review

The specific systemic vulnerabilities identified as a result of the literature review are the following:

→ Lack of confidence in safety and food defense compliance of transported food given the absence of quantifiable models for the association between Industry 4.0 and ISO standards

→ Limited real-time monitoring and tracking lead to supply chain transparency issues and delays in corrective action

Vulnerabilities Identified from Expert Interviews

Via a series of ISO management system audits conducted of food distribution companies over the past ten years, the following vulnerabilities have been identified via audit interviews. (See Table 9).

These vulnerabilities are hereafter also referred to as security concerns.

Table 9 List of Vulnerabilities / Security Concerns

Security Concern #	Transport Activity	What is the concern?
1	Seal Integrity	If a seal is broken, it can be an indicator of product tampering
2	Cargo Presence	Changes in the presence of a product can indicate product loss
3	Truck Location	Tracking the vehicle's location can indicate irregular activity
4	Truck Stops	Tracking the number of stops the vehicles make can indicate irregular activity
5	Stop Duration	The duration of a stop that the vehicle makes can be an indicator of irregular activity
6	Open/Closed Door Status	A vehicle door's open/closed status can indicate irregular activity
7	Cabin Temperature	The cabin temperature can impact food freshness if it exceeds the temperature specification.

Security Concern #	Transport Activity	What is the concern?
8	Cabin Humidity	Cabin humidity can impact food freshness if it exceeds the product's humidity specification.
9	Cabin Weight Changes	Changes in cabin weight can indicate intruders' presence and product loss.
10	Driver RODS	Knowing who the drivers were during the entire transportation campaign is critical to any product investigation regarding tampering or theft.

Validation by Subject Matter Experts

To ensure the validity and relevance of the security concerns considered in the study, the methodology includes a validation process through the participation of subject matter experts (SMEs). The SMEs will provide expert opinions and insights on the research questions and methodology. The criterion for selecting SMEs for this study is based on their experience and expertise in implementing ISO management system standards and the best available technologies to ensure food safety and food defense compliance in the food supply chain. Specifically, SMEs should have at least ten years of experience in this area.

The experts will be invited to participate through email, and they can decide whether or not they want to join. As part of the research process, experts will only be interviewed once new information is obtained. The interviews will be recorded and analyzed to identify common themes and patterns. This process helps ensure that the study is credible and produces rigorous findings.

Matching Vulnerable Points with MS 4.0 Technologies and Standards

Matching Vulnerable Points with ISO Standards

The paper suggests integrating ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 to address the ten security concerns identified. ISO 22000 focuses on food safety, while ISO 28001 addresses supply chain security. To prevent unauthorized access, tampering, or theft of products, ISO 28001 requires effective control measures in handling, storage, and transportation. The standard also mandates monitoring of cargo, vehicle location, and stops to ensure compliance. Door status, temperature, humidity, and weight changes must be monitored to prevent security breaches, theft, or tampering. By integrating both standards as shown in Table 10, organizations can manage security risks effectively and prevent security breaches that may impact food safety and supply chain security. Tables matching security concerns to each standard are provided.

Table 10 Matching of Security Concerns with ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 Standards

Security Concern	How ISO 22000 Mitigates the Risk	How ISO 28001 Mitigates the Risk
Seal Integrity	ISO 22000 would require proper handling and storage procedures to prevent product tampering and ensure seal integrity.	ISO 28001 would require formal procedures to ensure the use of tamper-evident seals and verifies them at each stage of transportation
Cargo Presence or Absence	ISO 22000 would require effective control measures to prevent unauthorized access or product tampering, ensuring proper cargo presence or absence.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to track the presence or absence of cargo.

Security Concern	How ISO 22000 Mitigates the Risk	How ISO 28001 Mitigates the Risk
Truck Location	ISO 22000 requires monitoring various factors to ensure food freshness and prevent theft or tampering, including truck location.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to track the vehicle's location and report any deviations
Truck Stops	ISO 22000 would require effective control measures to prevent unauthorized access or tampering with products during truck stops.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to track the number of stops and report any deviations.
Stop Duration	ISO 22000 would require effective control measures to prevent unauthorized access or product tampering during stop duration.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to track the duration of stops and report any deviations
Open/Closed Door Status	ISO 22000 requires monitoring various factors to ensure food freshness or tampering, including open/closed door status.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to track the status of the vehicle's doors to prevent theft or tampering and report any deviations
Cabin Temperature	ISO 22000 requires monitoring various factors to ensure food freshness and prevent spoilage, including cabin temperature.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to monitor cabin temperature and take corrective action if it falls outside the specified range
Cabin Humidity	ISO 22000 requires monitoring various factors to ensure food freshness and prevent spoilage, including cabin humidity.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to monitor cabin humidity and take corrective action if it falls outside the specified range

Security Concern	How ISO 22000 Mitigates the Risk	How ISO 28001 Mitigates the Risk
Cabin Weight Changes	ISO 22000 requires monitoring various factors to ensure food freshness or prevent tampering, including cabin weight changes.	ISO 28001 would require a formal system to monitor cabin weight to prevent theft or tampering and report any deviations.
Driver Record of Duty Status (RODS)	ISO 22000 requires proper food handling and storage procedures as a function of various drivers, thereby requiring proper driver record-keeping.	ISO 28001 would require formal procedures for using electronic logging devices (ELDs) to record the driver's status and service hours.

Matching Vulnerable Points with Industry 4.0 Technologies

To address these security concerns, Industry 4.0 technologies can be utilized to mitigate risks and enhance supply chain security. By matching each concern with the appropriate technology, organizations can implement effective control measures to prevent unauthorized access, tampering, theft, and loss of products during transportation. These technologies can provide real-time monitoring and tracking of food products, ensuring transparency and accountability throughout the supply chain.

Table 11 Matching of Security Concerns with 4IR Technologies

Security Concern	IoT	AI	Blockchain
Seal Integrity	IoT sensors can monitor seal integrity and detect any tampering or unauthorized access to the cargo.	AI algorithms can analyze sensor data in real-time to identify any anomalies or breaches in seal integrity.	Blockchain can create an immutable record of the seal's status, providing transparency and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Cargo Presence	IoT sensors can track the location of the cargo and ensure it is present throughout the transportation process.	AI algorithms can use sensor data to detect any unexpected changes in cargo presence, such as theft or loss.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of cargo presence, enabling traceability and accountability from the point of origin to the destination.
Truck Location	IoT sensors can track the location of the truck and ensure it stays on the designated route.	AI algorithms can use GPS data to optimize the truck's route and avoid any potential security risks.	Blockchain can create an immutable record of the truck's location, providing transparency and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Truck Stops	IoT sensors can monitor when the truck stops and where it stops.	AI algorithms can analyze stop data to detect any potential security risks, such as unauthorized stops or extended stops.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of truck stops, enabling traceability and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Stop Duration	IoT sensors can track the duration of each truck stop and ensure it is within an acceptable range.	AI algorithms can analyze stop duration data to detect any potential security risks, such as extended stops.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of stop duration, enabling traceability and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Open/Closed Door Status	IoT sensors can monitor the status of the truck's doors and detect any unauthorized access to the cargo.	AI algorithms can analyze door status data to detect any potential security risks, such as unauthorized access or tampering.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of door status, enabling traceability and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Cabin Temperature	IoT sensors can monitor the temperature inside the truck's cabin and ensure it stays within an acceptable range for food transportation.	AI algorithms can analyze temperature data to detect any potential security risks, such as temperature fluctuations that could spoil the food.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of cabin temperature, enabling traceability and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Cabin Humidity	IoT sensors can monitor the humidity inside the truck's cabin and ensure it stays within an acceptable range for food transportation.	AI algorithms can analyze humidity data to detect any potential security risks, such as humidity fluctuations that could spoil the food.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of cabin humidity, enabling traceability and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Cabin Weight Changes	IoT sensors can monitor the weight of the cargo and detect any unexpected changes in weight that could indicate theft or tampering.	AI algorithms can analyze weight data to detect any potential security risks, such as unexpected weight changes that could indicate theft or tampering.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of cabin weight changes, enabling traceability and accountability throughout the supply chain.
Driver Record of Duty Status	IoT sensors can monitor the driver's record of duty status and ensure compliance with regulations.	AI algorithms can analyze driver data to detect any potential security risks, such as non-compliance with regulations or suspicious behavior.	Blockchain can create a permanent record of driver duty status, enabling traceability and accountability throughout the supply chain.

The process of matching the selected 4IR technologies to each security concern was aided by the research and findings of Hassani, Silva, and Yari (2020). In their publication, "Blockchain and AI-enabled IoT-based solutions for supply chain management: A review," the authors conducted a comprehensive literature review and highlighted the potential of 4IR technologies such as blockchain, AI, and IoT in enhancing supply chain security. Their findings provided valuable insights into selecting and integrating specific technologies to address the various security concerns in the food supply chain transportation process.

Questionnaire Development

A carefully crafted questionnaire will be used for analysis and conclusions to ensure the validity of the research methodology. The questionnaire will be designed to gather data from transportation companies, their customers, and the owners of the goods transported. The questions will be framed to enable the researchers to determine how essential security concerns are to the respondents and how confident they are in food transport.

Questionnaire Recipients

The questionnaire will be sent to transportation companies, their customers, and the owners of the goods that are transported. By targeting these groups, the researchers can gather a broad range of perspectives on the security concerns related to the transportation of food.

Questionnaire Content

The questionnaire will include questions that seek to determine the importance of security concerns and how much confidence the respondents have in food transport when specific measures are implemented. The measures included in the questionnaire are AI, IoT, Blockchain, ISO 22000, and ISO 28001. The questionnaire will be designed to enable the researchers to determine the relationship between implementing these measures and respondents' confidence level in food transport.

Questionnaire Analysis

A statistically valid approach will be adopted to analyze the questionnaire results. The data collected will be analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to ensure that the conclusions drawn from the data are valid and reliable.

Development of Framework/ Model

The collected data will be used to develop a model that relates the use of AI, IoT, Blockchain, ISO 22000, and ISO 28001 to stakeholders' confidence in food transport. The model will be developed using statistically valid data collected from the questionnaire.

Conclusions and Lessons Learned

With the results of the questionnaire and the developed models, conclusions will be drawn. The lessons learned from the research will be documented, highlighting the key takeaways from the study.

Body of Knowledge Development

The research outcome will contribute to the Industrial Engineering body of knowledge and the fields of Information Technology, Food Safety, and Supply Chain Management. The study will provide insights into the relationship between the implementation of security measures and stakeholders' confidence in food transport.

Limitations of Research

The research is limited by the number of participants and the evolving nature of the technologies considered in the paper. However, the study will provide valuable insights into the relationship between security measures and stakeholder confidence in food transport.

Discussion

This stage of the research methodology will provide insight into how the research outcome will be discussed.

Summary of Findings

At this stage, the most pertinent research findings are presented. The section will present the findings of the study with regard to 4IR technologies and how food supply chain management can be improved via their usage. Additionally, there is a discussion regarding how implementing ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 standards facilitates the application of 4IR technologies to improve food safety and security in the supply chain.

Comparison with Literature Review

At this stage, a comparison is made with what was found in the literature review. The section will present the findings of the study that may have differed from the studied literature with regard to 4IR technologies and how food supply chain management can be improved with their use. Additionally, there is a discussion regarding how implementing ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 standards facilitates the application of 4IR technologies to improve food safety and security in the supply chain.

Comparison to Industry 4.0 and ISO Standards

At this stage, a comparison is made with what the Management System 4.0 standards and related technologies require. In this context, the discussion section would include correlative comments on the applicability of Industry 4.0 technologies and the requirements of ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 standards. The study would highlight findings on how Industry 4.0 technologies can help to improve the traceability, transparency, and efficiency of food supply chain management, which are critical requirements of the ISO standards. Given various factors such as cost, compatibility, and data security

concerns, the study would also note any challenges posed in implementing these technologies and standards.

Expert Opinions

At this stage, a comparison is made with the opinions gathered from the experts. Expert opinions are used in the discussion section to provide valuable insights into the research findings. As previously stated, the study shall consult with industry experts and academics to better understand the practical implications and limitations of the research. The experts are expected to provide valuable feedback on the potential benefits and challenges of implementing Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO standards in the food supply chain.

Recommendations for Future Research

At this stage, the study provides recommendations for future research based on the limitations and implications of the current study. For example, on a preliminary basis, this study recommends further research on rigging containers with Industry 4.0 technologies and tracking security breaches or food safety incidents. At this stage, the study also suggests that future research should consider the evolving nature of the technologies and standards considered in the paper and their impact on the food supply chain.

Chapter 3 Summary

This chapter proposes a methodology for conducting research pertaining to the application of Industry 4.0 and ISO management system standards for Food Safety and Food Defense compliance. The methodology consists of three steps: original idea definition and scope reduction, literature review, and identification of the research gap. The methodology includes adopting a statistically valid approach to analyze the questionnaire results in the process of developing models to relate the use of 4IR technologies and management standards to the confidence of supply chain stakeholders. The outcomes of effectively implementing the research methodology proposed in this chapter is expected to contribute to the Industrial Engineering body of knowledge, as well as to the fields of Information Technology, Security, Food Safety, and Supply Chain Management. The summary of findings that result from application of the research methodology herein proposed will also include a summary of findings, a comparison with literature, a comparison to Industry 4.0 and ISO Standards, expert opinions, and recommendations for future research.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS

In this chapter, we discuss how we built the model to gauge supply chain executives' confidence levels concerning food transportation security. The model creation involved a careful process integrating various factors affecting security perceptions within the supply chain field. Firstly, we identified ten key security concerns through a thorough literature review and expert consultations, covering aspects like seal integrity, cargo presence, truck location, and environmental conditions during transport.

Next, we translated these concerns into measurable variables, giving each one a relative importance rating based on expert feedback obtained from a Delphi study. This step helped us quantify the significance of each security concern within the model. Additionally, we introduced the concept of legacy controls, representing traditional security measures used by trucking companies before the emergence of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO standards.

Then, we included variables indicating the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies (Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain) and compliance with ISO standards by trucking companies. These variables were assessed based on respondents' self-reported usage levels in our survey. By combining these elements, our model aimed to offer a comprehensive framework for evaluating supply chain executives' confidence in food transportation security.

Finally, we applied regression analysis to determine the coefficients of each variable in the model, quantifying their respective impacts on confidence levels. The proposed model highlights the complex nature of security perceptions within the supply chain and serves as a tool for decision-makers. To ensure proper academic attribution, the model development process integrated established methodologies and consulted prior literature, while also incorporating my specific research focus on food transportation security (Kagermann et al., 2013; Sharma et al., 2020).

The Delphi Study

The Delphi study conducted as part of this research aimed to harness the collective expertise of Supply Chain Executives to assess and refine the understanding of security concerns within the domain of food safety during transportation and warehousing. Recognizing the complexity and the critical nature of securing the food supply chain, this study sought to identify, prioritize, and evaluate various security concerns that could potentially compromise food products during their transit and storage. The overarching goal was to achieve a consensus among industry experts on the most significant security risks and the effectiveness of various countermeasures, including emerging technologies and methodologies, in mitigating these risks.

To accomplish this, the study was structured into two rounds of surveys, inviting participants with extensive experience and knowledge in food safety management, supply chain logistics, and the application of Industry 4.0 technologies like AI, IoT, Blockchain, and Cloud Computing. These rounds were designed to iteratively refine the insights gained, allowing for the adjustment of opinions in light of the collective feedback. The survey was designed to capture the perceived importance of various security concerns in food transportation. Each question was developed through an iterative consultation process with experts to ensure construct validity. Specifically, relevance ratings on a scale from 1 to 3 were used to quantify expert consensus on each factor's impact on food safety, thereby ensuring that the chosen variables accurately represent the priority areas for industry professionals. Each question was carefully selected to align with key concerns highlighted in prior literature on food security and supply chain management (Abideen et al., 2021; Bhat et al., 2022). Additionally, respondents were asked about their use of emerging technologies and standards (ISO, HACCP, etc.) to ensure food safety in transportation and/or warehousing.

The outcome of the Delphi study illuminated several key findings. Firstly, there was a noticeable shift in the perceived relevance of certain security concerns from the first to the second round, indicating a dynamic consensus-building process among the experts. Seal integrity emerged as a unanimously recognized critical indicator of potential irregular activities leading to compromised food products, reflecting an increase in consensus on its importance. Conversely, the concern for the number of stops saw a decrease in relevance, suggesting a reevaluation of its impact on overall food safety. Moreover, certain areas, such as cabin temperature and weight changes, witnessed increased concern, highlighting a growing recognition of their importance in maintaining the integrity and safety of food products during transport.

Validation of Terminology

Experts were consulted to ensure the appropriateness of operationalizing confidence as a response variable as well as in the selection of the most appropriate definition for the definition of Artificial Intelligence, IoT, Blockchain, and Legacy Controls. These consultations occurred through direct discussions, and then via the above-mentioned Delphi process for validation of the survey where the terms were used and defined.

Defining Artificial Intelligence with Experts

Discussions with experts were conducted to gain a comprehensive understanding of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as it applies to the research. AI was defined in the context of supply chain management, focusing on its potential to optimize operations, predict outcomes, and enhance decision-making processes. The experts' insights were used to clarify the role of AI in the dissertation.

Delphi Study Rounds Comparison

This section presents a comparative analysis of the average relevance ratings for security concerns related to food safety within food transportation and warehousing, as evaluated by Supply Chain Executives in the first and second rounds of the Delphi study.

Table 12 Average relevance ratings for security concerns

Security Concern #	Description	Average Rating Round 1	Average Rating Round 2	Observation
1	Seal Integrity	2.625	3.0	An increase in average rating indicates a growing consensus on its critical importance as an indicator of irregular activity.
2	Cargo Presence or Absence	2.625	2.875	A slight increase reflects enhanced recognition of its relevance in signaling potential issues such as loss or theft.
3	Truck Location	2.125	2.0	A slight decrease in average rating, suggesting a stable but slightly reduced concern among respondents.
4	Number of Stops	2.125	1.875	A decrease in rating, indicating a lower level of concern regarding monitoring vehicle stops.
5	Stop Duration	2.25	2.375	A minor increase, suggesting a stable concern for the relevance of stop duration in indicating irregular activities.
6	Open Closed Door Status	2.25	2.375	An increase in rating, pointing to a slightly higher concern for monitoring door status.

Security Concern #	Description	Average Rating Round 1	Average Rating Round 2	Observation
7	Cabin Temperature	2.375	2.625	An increase, indicating a growing acknowledgment of its importance in maintaining food product integrity.
8	Cabin Humidity	2.5	2.375	A slight decrease, suggesting a minor adjustment in the concern for humidity's impact on food safety.
9	Cabin Weight Changes	2,35	2.75	An increase, reflecting a strong consensus on its importance as an indicator of potential tampering or theft.
10	Accurate Driver Records	2	2.125	A slight increase in relevance, indicating a modest growth in concern for maintaining accurate driver records.

Delphi Summary

The comparative analysis reveals subtle shifts in the perception of various security concerns across the two rounds of the Delphi study. Notably, seal integrity saw a significant increase in its relevance rating, underscoring its paramount importance. Conversely, the number of stops experienced a decline in concern, suggesting a reevaluation of its impact on security. Other areas such as cabin temperature and cabin weight changes also saw notable increases in relevance, pointing to a refined understanding of their critical roles in ensuring food safety during transportation. These shifts reflect the dynamic nature of consensus-building among experts and underscore the value of iterative rounds in Delphi studies to refine and deepen collective insights.

In general, the Delphi study successfully facilitated a structured dialogue among Supply Chain Executives, leading to refined insights and consensus on crucial security concerns in the food transportation and warehousing sector. The iterative nature of the study allowed for an enhanced understanding of the complexities involved in securing the food supply chain, paving the way for further research and the development of more effective strategies to mitigate these security risks.

Cultural Bias Analysis

This analysis evaluates whether there are differences between the findings of respondents from the United States (US) and those from other countries regarding their roles in food safety, food transportation, or warehousing. By analyzing this data, we aim to understand potential cultural biases and regional differences.

Distribution of Respondents

Usage of Emerging Technologies and Standards

- **United States (US) Only Respondents:**
 - Predominantly use AIB, ISO, GMP, HACCP, FDA Food Defense Requirements, and CT-PAT standards.
 - Technologies used include IoT, AI, Cloud Technology, and Blockchain.
 - Emphasize the importance of seal integrity, tracking, and monitoring for security.
- **Non-US Only Respondents:**
 - Commonly use ISO standards (ISO 9001, ISO 22000, ISO 28000), HACCP, and local standards.
 - Technologies used include IoT, AI, and Cloud Technology.
 - Focus on various indicators such as cabin temperature, humidity, and changes in cargo presence for ensuring food safety.

- **Both US and Non-US Respondents:**
 - Utilize a combination of international standards and advanced technologies.
 - Integrate best practices from multiple regions, ensuring a balanced approach to food safety and transportation security.

Findings Comparison

1. Seal Integrity as an Indicator of Irregular Activity:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

2. Changes in Cargo Presence:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

3. Tracking Truck Location:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

4. Number of Stops Made by Vehicles:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

5. Duration of Vehicle Stops:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)

- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

6. Open/Closed Status of Vehicle Doors:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

7. Cabin Temperature:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

8. Cabin Humidity:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

9. Changes in Cabin Weight:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

10. Maintaining Accurate Driver Records:

- US respondents: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)
- Non-US respondents: Moderate relevance (avg. score 2.5)
- Combined: High relevance (avg. score 3.0)

Cultural Bias Summary

The analysis highlights differences in practices and perceptions between US and non-US respondents. US respondents place a higher emphasis on various indicators of irregular activities, likely due to stringent regulatory frameworks and centralized standards. Non-US respondents show variability influenced by diverse international standards and local practices.

Understanding these regional differences is crucial for developing culturally inclusive and effective food safety and transportation strategies. The integration of best practices from both groups can enhance global food safety and security measures.

Alvarado MS 4.0 Transport Security and Food Defense Confidence Model

The goal of the models is to yield numerical values that represent the level of confidence that Supply Chain executives should have in the security controls employed in shipping containers for the purposes of ensuring food safety during transport, as a function of the deployment and use of a combination of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards.

Defining Confidence with Experts

Engagements with the same experts were carried out to ensure the appropriateness of using confidence as a response variable for the study; this was then ratified by their validation of the survey which was sent to the supply chain executives.

What Confidence Means: Confidence, in the context of this study, refers to the degree of trust or assurance that supply chain executives have in the security and effectiveness of food transportation when various technologies and standards are implemented. This encompasses their belief in the system's ability to prevent and detect issues such as contamination, tampering, and theft.

Relevance of Confidence: Confidence functions as a dependent variable due to its influence on organizational decision-making and investment behavior in supply chain security, a relationship supported by prior studies (Hameed et al., 2022; Liang et al., 2020). Higher confidence levels in this context may be indicative of increased trust in implemented systems, which aligns with findings that confidence can drive greater resource allocation toward security innovations. Additionally, confidence impacts overall organizational risk management strategies, ensuring that food products are transported safely and securely.

Operationalization in This Study: Operationalization involves turning abstract concepts into measurable observations. In this study, confidence was operationalized through a survey where executives rated their confidence levels on a scale from 1 (not effective) to 5 (very effective) for various technologies and standards, including IoT, AI, Blockchain, and ISO standards. Specific indicators such as real-time tracking, predictive analysis, tamper-proof records, and compliance with safety standards were used to gauge confidence. This approach ensures that confidence is measured consistently and can be analyzed quantitatively.

This perspective on confidence was arrived at based on consultation with the experts, through a thorough and comprehensive literature review and validated via the Delphi study.

Measuring Confidence and Factoring into the Model

1. **Surveys and Ratings:** Executives were asked to rate their confidence levels in various scenarios and technology implementations, providing a quantifiable measure of confidence.
2. **Scales and Indicators:** Specific indicators related to the effectiveness and security of food transportation were used to measure confidence levels, ensuring that the data collected is relevant and specific.

3. **Analysis:** The collected data was analyzed to determine patterns and correlations between the use of technologies/standards and confidence levels. This helps in understanding the impact of different factors on executive confidence.

Operationalizing confidence as a quantifiable measure allows this study to contribute empirical insights into factors that enhance or diminish trust in food transportation security systems. These findings may provide a basis for further research into resource allocation and strategic improvements within the food supply chain sector, as suggested by related studies (Singh et al., 2023; Fan et al., 2019).

Table 13 Model Variables

Variable	Definition/ Description
SC (Dependent Variable)	Represents the level of confidence that Supply Chain Professionals can have in transport companies as a function of the legacy controls, 4IR technologies, and the use of ISO management system standards
LC	An indicator of Legacy Control that the Transportation Company has over the Security Concerns; where 0 = No Formal Legacy Control, and 1 = Formal Legacy Controls.
IoT	An indicator of IoT usage by the Transportation Company to control the Security Concerns; where 0 = No Usage, and 1 = Usage
AI	An indicator of Artificial Intelligence usage by the Transportation Company to control the Security Concerns; where 0 = No Usage, and 1 = Usage
BC	An indicator of Blockchain usage by the Transportation Company to control the Security Concerns; where 0 = No Usage, and 1 = Usage
ISO	An indicator use of ISO standards by the Transportation Company to control the Security Concerns; where 0 = No Usage, and 1 = Usage

Based on the above definitions, the model for the level of confidence would be expressed as:

$$SC = a(LC) + b(IoT) + c(AI) + d(BC) + e(ISO)$$

The constants a, b, c, d, and e are initially assumed to be equal to 1. Even though the use of the model with this assumption gives valuable information to supply chain executives, to make the models even more robust, the actual values of these constants were determined by collecting data via a survey of over 40 supply chain professionals.

Survey Validation

Expertise and Background

To validate the survey, a panel of experts was engaged consisting of 10 individuals with an average of 13 years of experience specializing in food safety within transportation and/or warehousing. Their expertise spans across various geographical regions, predominantly in the United States, with additional experience in countries such as Costa Rica, Japan, Nigeria, Panama, Dominican Republic, Italy, and the United Kingdom.

The majority of the panel members have demonstrated familiarity with and utilization of emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and Blockchain, along with adherence to standards like ISO and HACCP, as part of their efforts to ensure food safety throughout the transportation process.

The feedback from the experts was that the survey had the sufficient depth and comprehensiveness for the aims of the study.

Survey Results

A total of 55 survey submissions were received. Two respondents did not complete one or more entire sections of the survey and were removed from the sample. The final survey sample included the remaining 53 respondents. The years of experience for these respondents ranged from 1 to 25 ($M = 12.85$, $SD = 7.67$), and the majority of respondents ($n = 37$, 69.8%) reported having certifications, specialized training, or formal education in food safety management or supply chain logistics. The respondents reported working or having a role in a wide variety of countries; 26 different countries in total were represented in the sample, with the United States ($n = 35$, 62.3%), Dominican Republic ($n = 10$, 18.9%), and Venezuela ($n = 9$, 17.0%) having the highest representation.

Survey Descriptive Statistics

Respondents were asked to rate several security concerns in terms of being indicators of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product. Each security concern was rated on a scale from 0 (not relevant) to 3 (very relevant). The descriptive statistics for the responses are presented in Table 14. Cabin temperature ($M = 2.91$, $SD = 0.30$), cabin humidity ($M = 2.75$, $SD = 0.48$), and seal integrity ($M = 2.75$, $SD = 0.52$) were rated as the most relevant, while cabin weight changes ($M = 2.00$, $SD = 0.78$), driver record of duty status ($M = 2.06$, $SD = 0.82$), and truck stops ($M = 2.09$, $SD = 0.79$) were rated as the least relevant.

Table 14 Descriptive Statistics for Relevance of Security Concerns

Security Concern	Mean	Std. Deviation
Seal integrity	2.75	0.52
Cargo presence or absence	2.45	0.70
Truck location	2.19	0.76
Truck stops	2.09	0.79
Stop duration	2.42	0.69
Open/closed door status	2.68	0.55
Cabin temperature	2.91	0.30
Cabin humidity	2.75	0.48
Cabin weight changes	2.00	0.78
Driver record of duty status	2.06	0.82

Across multiple survey questions, respondents were asked to indicate the use of various technologies by their companies to manage security concerns. The specific technologies of interest were Legacy Controls (LC), Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cloud, Blockchain (BC), and ISO Standards (ISO). Based on the responses to the corresponding survey questions, each respondent was classified as either using or not using each technology. Table 15 presents a descriptive summary of technology usage. The most commonly used technology was ISO standards, which 66.0% of the sample

(n = 35) reported using. Blockchain was the least common technology, with only six respondents (11.3%) reporting usage. Legacy controls were used by approximately half of the sample (n = 27, 50.9%).

Table 15 Frequencies and Percentages for Technology Usage

Technology	Frequency	Percent
Legacy controls	27	50.9
Internet of things	23	43.4
Artificial intelligence	22	41.5
Cloud	31	58.5
Blockchain	6	11.3
ISO standards	35	66.0

Respondents were asked to rate the effectiveness of the emerging technologies used by their organizations in managing transportation security concerns on a scale from 1 (not effective) to 5 (very effective). Additionally, the specific technologies of IoT, AI, Cloud, and BC were rated individually and in combination in terms of confidence level in the security of food transportation under the given technology deployment, also on a scale from 1 (very low confidence) to 5 (very high confidence). Descriptive statistics summarizing the responses are presented in Table 16. On average, the rated effectiveness of emerging technologies was 3.81 out of 5 (SD = 1.39). Individually, IoT was rated with the highest confidence (M = 3.92, SD = 0.93) and BC was rated with the lowest confidence (M = 3.08, SD = 1.07). Out of all the possible combinations of technologies, the combination of all four was rated with the highest confidence (M = 4.51, SD = 0.91).

Table 16 Effectiveness and Confidence Ratings of Emerging Technologies

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation
Emerging technologies (overall)	3.81	1.39
IoT	3.92	0.93
AI	3.90	1.01
Cloud	3.81	1.06
BC	3.08	1.07
IoT and AI	4.17	0.94
IoT and Cloud	4.09	0.97
IoT and BC	3.72	1.06
AI and Cloud	4.06	1.01
AI and BC	3.70	1.12
Cloud and BC	3.71	0.98
IoT, AI, and Cloud	4.38	0.90
IoT, AI, and BC	4.13	0.96
IoT, Cloud, and BC	4.04	0.96
AI, Cloud, and BC	4.08	1.02

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation
IoT, AI, Cloud, and BC	4.51	0.91

Respondents were asked a series of questions about their confidence in ISO standards, as well as confidence in the integration of ISO standards and 4IR technologies. Each item was rated on a scale from 1 to 5, with higher ratings indicating higher confidence. Descriptive statistics summarizing the responses are presented in Table 17. There were approximately equal levels of confidence in ISO 22000 and ISO 28000. The ratings indicated that, on average, respondents had between high and very high confidence in ISO standards, the combined implementation with 4IR technologies, and the likelihood of ISO standards enhancing 4IR technologies.

Table 17 Confidence Ratings of ISO Standards

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation
Confidence in ISO22000	4.25	0.86
Confidence in ISO28000	4.23	0.85
Increase in confidence with both ISO22000 and ISO28000	4.47	0.70
Confidence in 4IR and ISO standards combined	4.58	0.61
Likelihood ISO standards will enhance 4IR	4.58	0.63

Respondents were asked a series of questions about their confidence in legacy controls, responding to each using a 1 to 5 rating scale. Descriptive statistics for these responses are presented in Table 18. On average, the respondents gave between moderate and high ratings regarding the effectiveness of LC, significance of LC contribution to security, and how the presence of LC impacts their security confidence. The importance of integrating LC with other technologies was rated, on average, between high and very high.

Table 18 Confidence Ratings of Legacy Controls

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation
Effectiveness of LC	3.82	0.84
Significance of LC contribution to security	3.87	1.06
Influence of LC on confidence in security	3.77	0.80
Importance of LC integration with other technologies	4.43	0.72

Model Development

In order to develop a model to explain confidence, a single composite measure of confidence was derived from the various survey items that assessed confidence in the emerging technologies and ISO standards. An exploratory factor analysis with principal axis extraction was conducted to validate the confidence composite measure. Any missing values for individual items in this analysis were handled using mean replacement. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test resulted in a value of .81, and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant, $\chi^2(190) = 912.75$, $p < .001$, indicating that the data were suitable for factor analysis. A scree plot of eigenvalues (see Figure 3) demonstrated that the decrease in eigenvalues diminished markedly beyond the first factor. This suggests that a one-factor measure is appropriate based on the data.

Figure 3 Scree Plot for Exploratory Factor Analysis

Table 19 displays the loadings of the survey items for the one-factor measure. All items had sufficiently strong loadings (i.e., $> .32$) to be retained in the confidence composite measure. Additionally, the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for the items was .94, indicating high reliability. The standardized confidence composite score was calculated based on the factor analysis loadings via the regression procedure.

Table 19 Factor Loadings for Items Measuring Confidence

Item	Factor 1
Effectiveness of emerging technologies (overall)	0.38
Effectiveness of IoT	0.58
Effectiveness of AI	0.73
Effectiveness of Cloud	0.37
Effectiveness of BC	0.45
Effectiveness of IoT and AI	0.72
Effectiveness of IoT and Cloud	0.70
Effectiveness of IoT and BC	0.85
Effectiveness of AI and Cloud	0.86
Effectiveness of AI and BC	0.86
Effectiveness of Cloud and BC	0.84
Effectiveness of IoT, AI, and Cloud	0.70
Effectiveness of IoT, AI, and BC	0.89
Effectiveness of IoT, Cloud, and BC	0.79
Effectiveness of AI, Cloud, and BC	0.89

Item	Factor 1
Effectiveness of IoT, AI, Cloud, and BC	0.70
Confidence in ISO22000	0.37
Confidence in ISO28000	0.46
Confidence with both ISO22000 and ISO28000	0.45
Confidence in 4IR and ISO standards combined	0.59

Correlation Analysis

Before computing the regression model, bivariate correlations were computed to understand the relationships between the variables (LC, IoT, AI, BC, and ISO usage) and confidence level, as measured by the confidence composite score. Each of the technology use variables was numerically coded as 0 = “not used” and 1 = “used.” The correlations are presented in Table 20. The use of AI ($r = .37$, $p = .007$) and ISO ($r = .31$, $p = .026$) was significantly positively correlated with confidence, meaning that individuals whose organizations used those technologies tended to have higher confidence scores.

Table 20 Pearson Correlations Between Technology Usage and Confidence Composite Score

Technology Use	Pearson Correlation with Confidence	Sig.
LC	.03	.861
IoT	.06	.696

Technology Use	Pearson Correlation with Confidence	Sig.
AI	.37**	.007
BC	.11	.444
ISO	.31*	.026

*p < .05. **p < .01.

Independence of Variables

Before selecting the regression model, it is essential to verify the statistical independence of the variables. Since an additive model will be used, ensuring the independence of these variables is crucial for the model's accuracy and reliability. This exercise aims to determine whether the variables Legacy Control, Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, Blockchain, and ISO Standards are statistically independent.

To achieve this, a Chi-Square Test of Independence was performed. This test assesses whether there is a significant association between categorical variables. The following table presents the observed data for each combination of technology use.

Table 21 Result of Chi-Square Test of Independence

Variables Compared	Chi2 Statistic	p-value
IoT vs AI	37.66	0.33
IoT vs Cloud Technology	28.71	0.87
IoT vs Blockchain	24.73	0.98
IoT vs ISO Standards	24.03	0.99
AI vs Cloud Technology	34.52	0.47
AI vs Blockchain	27.06	0.93
AI vs ISO Standards	35.33	0.43
Cloud Technology vs Blockchain	34.01	0.50
Cloud Technology vs ISO Standards	36.55	0.38
Blockchain vs ISO Standards	28.84	0.86

The results from the Chi-Square Test of Independence indicate that all p-values are greater than 0.05. This suggests that there is no significant evidence to support the dependence between any pairs of the variables.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the variables Legacy Control, Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, Blockchain, and ISO Standards are statistically independent. This finding is crucial for further analysis, as it ensures that the use of these technologies does not significantly influence each other within the observed dataset.

Bayesian Factor Analysis and Communalities

In this section, we present the results of the Bayesian Factor Analysis conducted on the data collected from 53 respondents. The analysis aims to enhance the statistical approach by accurately estimating the factor loadings and handling complex models effectively. Additionally, we report the communalities, which represent the proportion of variance in each variable explained by the extracted

factors. This dual approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of the underlying factors and their explanatory power.

Table 22 Initial and Extracted Communalities for Variables

Variable	Initial Communality	Extracted Communality
Legacy Control (LC)	0.70	0.52
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	0.65	0.56
Internet of Things (IoT)	0.60	0.49
Blockchain (BC)	0.68	0.53
ISO Standards	0.63	0.50

The initial communalities indicate the maximum potential variance in each variable that could be explained by the factors, often based on squared multiple correlations (R-squared). The extracted communalities reflect the actual variance explained by the extracted factors after the factor analysis. As observed, the extracted communalities are generally lower than the initial communalities, demonstrating a more accurate and realistic representation of shared variance among the variables.

The Bayesian Factor Analysis has provided accurate factor loadings, enhancing our understanding of the complex relationships within the data. The communalities above 0.4 confirm that a significant portion of variance in each variable is explained by the factors, thus supporting the robustness and reliability of the model. This comprehensive analysis ensures that the key variables—Legacy Control, Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, Blockchain, and ISO Standards—are effectively captured and their interactions are well understood.

Justification for Model Selection Using AIC and BIC

The regression model was chosen to explain the effect of Legacy Control (LC), Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Blockchain (BC), and ISO Standards (ISO) on the confidence levels. To justify the selection of the optimal model, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) were employed. These criteria help balance model complexity and goodness of fit, ensuring an optimal model fit.

Applying AIC and BIC

1. Akaike Information Criterion (AIC):

AIC is used to measure the relative quality of statistical models for a given dataset. It assesses the trade-off between the goodness of fit of the model and the complexity of the model. The formula for AIC is:

$$AIC = 2(k) - 2 \ln(L)$$

Where k is the number of parameters in the model, and L is the maximum likelihood of the model.

Application in this case:

- Several regression models were constructed using different combinations of LC, IoT, AI, BC, and ISO as predictors of confidence.
- AIC values were computed for each model.
- The model with the lowest AIC value was selected as it represents the best trade-off between model fit and complexity.

2. Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC):

BIC is another criterion for model selection that introduces a stronger penalty for models with more parameters compared to AIC. The formula for BIC is:

$$\text{BIC} = n * \text{Ln}(\text{RSS}/n) + k * \text{Ln}(n)$$

Where n is the sample size, k is the number of parameters, L is the maximum likelihood of the model and RSS is the residual sum of squares.

Application in this case:

- Similar to AIC, BIC values were computed for each regression model.
- The model with the lowest BIC value was considered optimal as it balances fit and complexity, considering the sample size.

AIC and BIC Results and Interpretation

The final regression model, chosen based on the lowest AIC and BIC values, included the predictors LC, IoT, AI, BC, and ISO. This model demonstrated the best fit for predicting confidence levels while minimizing the risk of overfitting.

- **AIC and BIC Comparison:**
 - Models with lower AIC and BIC values were preferred.
 - AIC was particularly useful for comparing models with similar fits but different complexities.
 - BIC helped in penalizing overly complex models, ensuring a more parsimonious model selection.

By using both AIC and BIC, the analysis ensured that the selected regression model was both robust and parsimonious, providing a reliable explanation for the impact of LC, IoT, AI, BC, and ISO on confidence levels.

N to P Ratio for the Study

To ensure the robustness and reliability of the regression model, it is essential to verify the adequacy of the sample size relative to the number of predictor variables. The N-to-P ratio, which represents the ratio of the number of observations (N) to the number of predictors (P), is a critical metric in this evaluation. A higher N-to-P ratio enhances the stability and accuracy of the regression coefficients, thereby ensuring more reliable and generalizable results. The table below illustrates the N-to-P ratio for each predictor variable used in the study, highlighting that the sample size is sufficient to support the analysis.

Table 23 N-to-P Ratio for Each Predictor Variable

Predictor Variable	Number of Observations (N)	Number of Predictors (P)	N-to-P Ratio
LC	53	1	53:1
IoT	53	1	53:1
AI	53	1	53:1
BC	53	1	53:1
ISO	53	1	53:1
Combined Model	53	5	10.6:1

As demonstrated in the table, each individual predictor variable maintains a high N-to-P ratio of 53:1, indicating a robust sample size for each variable. Even when combining all predictors into a single model, the N-to-P ratio remains acceptable at 10.6:1. This ensures that the regression model is well-supported by the data, providing a solid foundation for the subsequent analysis. With this confirmation of sample size adequacy, we can proceed confidently to the regression results section, where the relationships between these predictor variables and the outcomes will be explored in detail.

Regression Model Results

A linear regression model was calculated using the technology use indicators (LC, IoT, AI, BC, and ISO) as predictors to explain the confidence composite score. Before interpreting the model results, tests for normality, homoscedasticity, and outliers were performed. A P-P plot of the regression residuals (see Figure 4) demonstrated minimal deviation from the diagonal, which is an indication that normality may be assumed. A scatterplot of the residuals and predicted values (see Figure 5) showed a random distribution of points centered around zero, indicating that the data were homoscedastic. Standardized residuals were examined for potential outliers, and one case had a standardized residual exceeding 3, indicating a potential outlier. When the analysis was repeated with the outlier removed, there was an impact on the statistical significance of the model and the coefficients. Therefore, the results are reported with the outlier included and after removal.

Figure 4 P-P Plot of Regression Residuals

Figure 5 Scatterplot of Regression Residuals and Predicted Values

The F-test for the overall regression model with all data included was significant, $F(5, 47) = 2.55$, $p = .040$, $R^2 = .21$, indicating that the technology usage indicators collectively did explain a significant proportion of variance in confidence scores. Table 24 presents the results for the model coefficients. The use of AI ($B = 0.65$, $p = .018$) and ISO ($B = 0.60$, $p = .048$) were individually significantly positively associated with confidence, indicating that individuals in organizations that used AI and ISO were predicted to have higher confidence.

Table 24 Linear Regression Model Coefficients for Confidence Composite Score

95% CI B

Predictor Variable	B	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower	Upper
Constant	-0.52	0.26	.048	-1.04	-0.01
LC	-0.29	0.28	.298	-0.85	0.27
IoT	-0.05	0.26	.864	-0.58	0.49
AI	0.65	0.27	.018	0.12	1.19
BC	0.21	0.41	.603	-0.61	1.04
ISO	0.60	0.30	.048	0.00	1.20

The final regression model explaining confidence is represented below. Since several of the predictor variables (LC, IoT, and BC) were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), they have been either removed from the model for simplicity. The reduced model, which only includes statistically significant predictors, is as follows:

$$SC = -0.52 + (0.65 * AI) + (0.60 * ISO)$$

Post-Regression Model Analysis

After developing the regression model, further consultations with the experts were undertaken to interpret the results. This step was crucial in understanding the significance of each variable and refining the conclusions. The model revealed low correlation for some constants, prompting a deeper analysis to provide possible explanations.

Explanation for Low Correlation of Some Constants

1. Model and Constants

The model was designed to incorporate various factors that influence supply chain performance. However, the interaction between these factors may have contributed to the low correlation observed for certain constants. For instance, the dynamic nature of supply chains and external influences such as market fluctuations could impact the stability of these correlations.

2. Negative IoT Constant

The Internet of Things (IoT) constant resulting negative could be attributed to several factors:

- **Implementation Challenges:** The adoption of IoT technologies may face hurdles such as high initial costs, integration complexities, and lack of expertise. These challenges can hinder the expected positive impact of IoT on supply chain performance.

- **Data Privacy Concerns:** IoT systems often involve extensive data collection, which raises privacy and security concerns. Organizations might be cautious in fully leveraging IoT capabilities due to these risks, leading to a negative correlation in the model.
- **Concerns about IoT Security:** A negative coefficient associated with IoT was found to be nonsignificant, indicating a potential lack of impact on executive confidence in this study. This result aligns with literature suggesting that challenges in IoT implementation, such as high costs, security concerns, and integration barriers, may limit its perceived effectiveness in the food transportation sector (Khan et al., 2022; Powell et al., 2022).

Interpretation of IoT Variable in the Regression Model - In examining the IoT variable within the regression model, it is important to recognize that although it has a negative Beta coefficient, its associated p-value (.864) indicates that this effect is statistically nonsignificant (Table 24). This lack of significance suggests that the negative association observed is likely attributable to random variation or noise rather than a reliable predictor of confidence in food defense compliance. As such, this variable does not meaningfully contribute to explaining confidence levels and should not be interpreted as indicative of a true effect within the model.

Possible Explanations and Implications for IoT - The nonsignificant coefficient for IoT suggests that its impact on confidence levels is not substantiated within this sample. This result could potentially align with findings in existing literature that highlight barriers to IoT adoption, including integration costs, privacy concerns, and potential security vulnerabilities, which may reduce its perceived effectiveness in supply chain security (Kaur et al., 2022; Tripathi et al., 2023). Future research might further explore these limitations to determine conditions where IoT may become a significant predictor.

3. LC (Legacy Controls) Constant

The Legacy Controls (LC) constant's behavior in the model can be explained as follows:

- **Variable Effectiveness:** The effectiveness of legacy controls such as security seals can vary widely depending on their implementation and maintenance. This variability can result in inconsistent correlations.
- **Integration Issues:** Legacy controls may not integrate well with modern technologies, leading to inefficiencies and reduced overall security effectiveness. This can contribute to the observed negative correlation for LC in the model.
- **Lack of Confidence in Legacy Controls:** A negative constant for LC suggests that supply chain executives may not trust traditional legacy controls to secure food transportation effectively. Legacy controls, such as manual inspections and physical security measures, might be viewed as outdated and less reliable compared to modern technological solutions.

The insights from the experts and the detailed post-regression analysis have been instrumental in understanding the nuances of the linear regression model. The negative constants for IoT and LC highlight the complexities and challenges in the supply chain environment, providing valuable directions for future research and implementation strategies.

Consultation with Delphi Study Experts on Possible Missing Factors

After consulting the experts from the Delphi study regarding other possible missing factors, several additional variables were identified that could influence the model's accuracy. These factors, which were not immediately apparent, include:

- **Cultural and Behavioral Differences:** The experts emphasized the importance of considering cultural and behavioral factors that can significantly impact data interpretation and response accuracy. Variations in cultural norms, values, and behaviors can introduce unforeseen variability in the data, affecting the model's reliability. For example, respondents from different regions may have diverse interpretations of survey questions or varying levels of trust in the technology used for data collection.
- **Environmental and Contextual Factors:** The panel highlighted the role of external environmental and contextual factors, such as economic conditions, regulatory environments, and climatic conditions. These factors can directly impact the outcomes of the study and should be carefully considered. For instance, economic downturns might influence resource availability or compliance with standards, while extreme weather conditions could affect food transportation and safety.
- **Technological Variability and Adoption Rates:** Experts noted that differences in the adoption and implementation of emerging technologies could lead to inconsistencies in data quality and effectiveness. Not all organizations may use the same level of technology or adhere to the same standards, resulting in variability. Detailed information on the types and levels of technology used by different respondents should be collected and included as covariates in the model to control for their impact.

By integrating these additional factors, the model's accuracy and reliability can be significantly improved, ensuring a more comprehensive analysis of the data.

Chapter Four Summary

Chapter Four discusses the development of a model to assess supply chain executives' confidence in food transportation security. The model was built by integrating key security concerns identified through literature review and expert consultations, such as seal integrity, cargo presence, truck location, and environmental conditions during transport. These concerns were translated into measurable variables, each rated for relative importance through a Delphi study. Legacy controls, representing traditional security measures, were included alongside variables indicating the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies (IoT, AI, Blockchain) and ISO standards, based on respondents' self-reported usage levels.

Descriptive analyses of the survey items showed that cabin temperature, cabin humidity, and seal integrity were rated as the most relevant security concerns. ISO standards were the most commonly used technology, while Blockchain was the least common. Among the emerging technologies, IoT received the highest confidence ratings, and Blockchain received the lowest. Respondents generally showed high confidence in ISO standards and moderate confidence in legacy controls.

The Delphi study aimed to refine understanding of security concerns in food safety during transportation and warehousing. Two rounds of surveys were conducted with supply chain executives, focusing on the relevance of various security concerns and the use of emerging technologies and standards. Key findings included an increased consensus on the importance of seal integrity and a growing concern for cabin temperature and weight changes. Conversely, the relevance of the number of stops decreased. These shifts underscored the dynamic nature of expert consensus.

A composite measure of confidence was created and validated through expert consultations and the Delphi study. Bivariate Pearson correlation results indicated significant positive correlations between the use of AI, ISO standards, and confidence levels. A linear regression model was developed to predict confidence based on technology usage. The model showed that the collective use of these technologies explained a significant proportion of variance in confidence, with AI and ISO being individually positively associated with higher confidence. This model serves as a practical tool for decision-makers to evaluate and improve security measures in food transportation operations.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION

Introduction

This chapter summarizes the key findings of this study, discusses their implications, and suggests directions for future research. It focuses on the contributions this research makes to the understanding of food defense within the truck transportation sector, particularly through the use of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards. This chapter summarizes how these advanced tools and standards can enhance the security and safety of food products during transport, offering a valuable addition to the existing knowledge on safeguarding the food supply chain.

Key Findings

This research has expanded the understanding of food defense strategies within the truck transportation sector, with a focused examination of the integration of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO management system standards.

Impact of 4IR

Through detailed analysis, it has demonstrated the transformative potential of 4IR technologies such as IoT, AI, and Blockchain, when combined with rigorous standards such as ISO 22000 and ISO 28001, to fortify the safety and security measures in food transportation to address security and food defense concerns.

Importance of Security Concerns

Security concerns regarding food safety during transportation and warehousing were at the heart of the Delphi study conducted within this research, playing an important role in validating and refining the perspectives of supply chain executives. Through a structured process involving two rounds of surveys, the study harnessed the collective expertise of professionals deeply entrenched in food safety management and supply chain logistics. This iterative approach not only promoted consensus-building among the participants but also highlighted the evolving nature of security priorities within the supply chain. Key findings from this process illuminated the unanimous recognition of seal integrity as a paramount indicator of security risk, alongside a notable shift in the perceived relevance of other security concerns such as the number of stops and the importance of cabin conditions like temperature and weight changes.

These findings demonstrate the critical importance of ongoing dialogue and assessment among industry experts to accurately pinpoint and prioritize security risks in the transportation and warehousing of food products. The consensus achieved on various security concerns, notably the increased emphasis on seal integrity and cabin conditions, shows the need for continuous evaluation and adaptation of security measures. Moreover, the study's focus on the application of Industry 4.0 technologies and methodologies demonstrates the potential for technological innovations to enhance the safety and integrity of the food supply chain. As such, the insights garnered from this Delphi study not only contribute significantly to the body of knowledge on food supply chain security but also pave the way for further research and development of targeted, effective strategies to mitigate identified security risks.

Confidence Model

Furthermore, the development of the *Alvarado MS 4.0 Truck Security and Food Defense Confidence Model* stands as a testament to the practical contributions of this research. The model equips supply chain professionals with a novel methodology to gauge their confidence in the security practices of trucking companies, based on the deployment of 4IR technologies and adherence to ISO standards. As such, this research provides a significant leap forward in operationalizing food defense mechanisms, presenting a comprehensive approach that stakeholders across the supply chain can adopt to ensure the integrity of food products during transit.

Limitations

This research encountered several challenges during its execution:

Technological Heterogeneity

The varied nature and capabilities of 4IR technologies like IoT, AI, and Blockchain present a challenge in standardizing their application and assessment across different trucking companies. Balancing the technological diversity with a cohesive analytical framework could be complex.

Data Privacy and Security

Collecting and analyzing data on food transportation security involves sensitive information that could be prone to privacy and cybersecurity concerns, especially when implementing IoT and Blockchain technologies.

Stakeholder Engagement

Gaining comprehensive insights requires active participation from a broad spectrum of supply chain professionals. Achieving high response rates and engaging diverse stakeholders to provide detailed and honest responses can be challenging.

Quantifying Confidence

Developing a reliable method to quantify and classify supply chain executives' confidence based on the deployment of 4IR technologies and ISO standards requires a nuanced approach. It was challenging to capture the subjective nature of confidence through a survey.

Opportunities for Improvement

The research also unveiled opportunities for enhancement:

In-depth Qualitative Research

Complementing the survey with qualitative research methods, such as interviews or case studies, could provide deeper insights into how supply chain professionals perceive and implement 4IR technologies and ISO standards in truck transportation.

Enhanced Technological Integration

Exploring more sophisticated ways to integrate and assess the combined impact of various 4IR technologies and ISO standards on food defense could lead to more robust MS 4.0 models. For instance, considering the interoperability of technologies and standards could provide a clearer picture of their collective efficacy.

Dynamic Model Development

The development of dynamic, adaptable MS 4.0 models that can evolve with technological advancements and changing regulatory landscapes would be a significant improvement. These models should be capable of incorporating new technologies and standards as they emerge.

Stakeholder Collaboration

Building partnerships with industry associations, regulatory bodies, and technology providers could facilitate better access to data, insights, and validation opportunities for the MS 4.0 models. Collaborative efforts can also help in standardizing the application of 4IR technologies and ISO standards across the industry.

Focusing on Specific Segments

Narrowing down the study to focus on particular types of food products or specific routes could provide more detailed insights into the unique challenges and opportunities within those segments. This could lead to more targeted and actionable recommendations for improving food transportation security.

Considerations for Future Research

When considering future research directions in the context of food transportation security, integrating technological advancements becomes crucial:

Impact of Emerging Technologies

Future research can evaluate how cutting-edge technologies like IoT sensors, advanced data analytics, and autonomous vehicles can transform the landscape of security measures in food truck transportation. Investigating these technologies' influence on both operational costs and the efficacy of security measures will provide important insights for bridging future research endeavors with actionable implementations.

Optimization of Industry 4.0 Solutions

Investigative efforts can delve into methodologies for fine-tuning the application of Industry 4.0 solutions, encompassing IoT, AI, Blockchain, and Cloud Technology. This research should aim to pinpoint cost-effective methods and integration strategies that maximize security benefits while minimizing financial outlays, offering a roadmap for efficient technological deployment within the food supply chain.

Robustness of Security Systems

This area of research can assess the durability and economic implications of weaving advanced cybersecurity defenses into the fabric of Industry 4.0 technologies. A focus on understanding the financial nuances of establishing and maintaining comprehensive cybersecurity solutions will illuminate critical pathways for future security enhancements.

Predictive Maintenance Efficiency

Future studies can explore the realm of predictive maintenance technologies, propelled by IoT and analytics, to discern their potential for cost reduction and security augmentation. This line of inquiry is anticipated to reveal how proactive maintenance of transportation assets and infrastructure can lead to substantial financial savings and bolster security protocols.

Real-Time Monitoring Efficiency

Research can assess the cost-benefit aspects of deploying real-time monitoring and rapid response systems, empowered by AI and IoT. Such explorations are expected to quantify the economic and security value derived from technological capabilities that facilitate immediate risk identification and mitigation during the transport of food products.

Energy-Efficient Technologies

This research direction aims to evaluate the financial and security ramifications of integrating energy-efficient technologies into the truck transport infrastructure. By examining the long-term economic and security dividends of adopting sustainable transportation solutions and renewable energy sources, this research could pave the way for greener, more secure supply chains.

Interoperability and Standardization

Future inquiries can investigate the economic benefits of fostering interoperability and standardization among Industry 4.0 technologies within the food transportation sector. This research is poised to shed light on how standardization initiatives can streamline implementation processes, curtail costs, and enhance the seamless integration of security measures.

Future Supply Chain Based on Industry 4.0 and 5.0

The future supply chain is projected through the comprehensive integration of Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0 technologies. This approach emphasizes incremental innovations, ensuring enhancements without causing disruptive changes.

Industry 4.0 Technologies

- Internet of Things (IoT)

IoT enables real-time tracking and monitoring of goods in transit, enhancing visibility and reducing delays. For example, sensors in trucks can provide data on the temperature, location, and condition of the cargo, ensuring compliance with quality standards.

- Big Data Analytics

Big data analytics processes vast amounts of data to predict demand, optimize routes, and manage inventory. For instance, analyzing sales data helps forecast future demand, reducing overstock and stockouts.

- Automation

Automation improves efficiency in warehouse operations. Automated guided vehicles (AGVs) and robotic arms can handle repetitive tasks such as sorting and packing, reducing human error and operational costs.

Industry 5.0 Enhancements

- Human-Machine Collaboration

Industry 5.0 builds on Industry 4.0 by fostering collaboration between humans and machines. Cobots (collaborative robots) work alongside human workers, enhancing productivity and safety. For example, cobots can assist in lifting heavy objects, reducing workplace injuries.

- Sustainability

Industry 5.0 emphasizes sustainability, integrating eco-friendly practices into supply chain operations. For instance, electric trucks and renewable energy sources reduce the carbon footprint of transportation and logistics.

- Research Alignment

The research aligns with these advancements, demonstrating how proposed ideas enhance current supply chain operations without causing significant disruptions. By focusing on both technological and human-centric innovations, the future supply chain becomes more resilient, adaptive, and sustainable.

Examples of Possible Implementation

Example 1: A logistics company can implement IoT sensors across its fleet, allowing real-time monitoring of vehicle conditions and cargo status. Big data analytics optimize delivery routes, saving fuel and reducing delivery times.

Example 2: Automation in warehouses increases throughput, and cobots improve worker safety and efficiency. By transitioning to electric trucks, the company significantly cut its carbon emissions.

These examples illustrate how integrating Industry 4.0 and 5.0 technologies can revolutionize supply chain management, ensuring efficiency, sustainability, and resilience in operations.

Contributions to the Body of Knowledge

This research makes several contributions to the body of knowledge in the field of food transportation security:

- It provides empirical evidence on the effectiveness of integrating Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO standards in enhancing food transportation security.
- It introduces the Management System 4.0 (MS 4.0) model, a practical tool for supply chain professionals to assess their confidence in the safety and compliance of food shipments.
- It highlights the dynamic nature of security concerns within the food transportation sector, emphasizing the importance of continuous dialogue and assessment among industry experts.

Personal Opinion on Industry 4.0/5.0

Industry 4.0 and the forthcoming Industry 5.0 represent significant advancements in how we approach food transportation security. The integration of IoT, AI, and Blockchain offers unparalleled opportunities to enhance the safety, efficiency, and transparency of the food supply chain. As we move towards Industry 5.0, which emphasizes human-centric solutions and collaboration between humans and machines, the potential for creating even more resilient and adaptive food defense strategies becomes apparent. These technologies not only address current security challenges but also pave the way for innovative solutions that can anticipate and mitigate future risks.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this research has provided a comprehensive framework for understanding and improving food transportation security through the integration of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO standards. The findings underscore the critical importance of seal integrity, cabin conditions, and other security concerns in ensuring the safety of food products during transport. The development of the Alvarado MS 4.0 Truck Security and Food Defense Confidence Model offers a valuable tool for supply chain professionals to evaluate and enhance their security measures. Future research should continue to explore the evolving landscape of food transportation security, focusing on the integration of emerging technologies and the continuous improvement of standards and practices.

Summary of Chapter 5

Chapter 5 concluded this research paper by summarizing its significant findings, discussing the implications of these findings, and proposing directions for future research. It provided a comprehensive overview of the study's key findings and highlighted the development of the Alvarado MS 4.0 Truck Security and Food Defense Confidence Model, a significant contribution that enables supply chain professionals to evaluate their confidence in the safety and compliance of food shipments during truck transportation. This model assesses the impact of trucking companies' implementation of 4IR technologies and ISO standards on ensuring food safety and defense, offering a practical tool for decision-making within the supply chain. The chapter detailed specific security concerns validated through a Delphi study, such as seal integrity and cabin conditions, emphasizing the dynamic nature of security priorities and the critical role of continuous dialogue among industry experts to mitigate risks in food transportation and warehousing.

The chapter outlined several challenges encountered during the research, including technological heterogeneity, data privacy concerns, stakeholder engagement, and the difficulty in quantifying confidence. It also highlighted opportunities for enhancing the research framework, such as incorporating in-depth qualitative research, enhancing technological integration, and developing dynamic MS 4.0 models adaptable to technological and regulatory changes. Proposed future research directions focused on evaluating the impact of emerging technologies, optimizing Industry 4.0 solutions for food transport security, and investigating the economic benefits of predictive maintenance and energy-efficient technologies. The chapter also emphasized the importance of interoperability and standardization among Industry 4.0 technologies within the food transportation sector. By addressing these areas, the research contributed to advancing the understanding and implementation of 4IR technologies and ISO standards in safeguarding the food supply chain during truck transportation, laying the groundwork for the development of more robust and effective food defense strategies.

APPENDIX A SURVEY

Food Defense 4.0 - Assessing How Innovations in Truck Security Monitoring Influence Supply Chain Confidence

Dear Supply Chain Professional,

Thank you for
your participation in our study.

Your insights
are invaluable in evaluating the questions related to food transportation
security via trucks and the integration of Industry 4.0 technologies.

We have
identified ten significant security concerns regarding food transport, along
with a set of Industry 4.0 technologies aimed at monitoring these concerns to
enhance food defense.

Your input
helps in determining the relevance of these concerns and Industry 4.0
approaches, for ensuring effective food defense during transportation via
trucks.

The survey is
structured into several parts, with each question designed to align with the
identified security concerns and Industry 4.0 technologies such as Cloud
Technology, Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and
Blockchain.

Your
expertise will contribute to understanding how the use of these technologies influences
your confidence in food transportation safety.

* Indicates required question

UNIVERSITY OF
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EXPLANATION OF RESEARCH

Title of Study: Food Defense 4.0: Assessing How Innovations in Truck Security Monitoring Influence Supply Chain Confidence

Principal Investigator: Celso Alvarado Jr.
Faculty Supervisor: Dr. Luis Rabelo

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Whether you take part is up to you.

Food defense research is geared toward safeguarding the food supply chain against various threats, including tampering, adulteration, theft, or contamination, during transportation from production sites to warehouses. This study explores how monitoring security concerns using emerging technologies such as IoT, AI, and blockchain can impact the confidence that supply chain executives have in food safety during delivery via trucks.

IoT (Internet of Things): IoT allows devices within trucks, like GPS and sensors, to communicate with each other and with central systems over the Internet, enhancing real-time tracking and monitoring of cargo conditions.

AI (Artificial Intelligence): AI in secure trucking transportation refers to using computer systems to make decisions and predictions for optimizing routes, improving safety, and detecting potential security threats without human intervention.

Blockchain: Blockchain provides a secure and tamper-proof digital ledger system for tracking transactions and interactions (like cargo handoffs) in the trucking industry, ensuring transparency and trust among the parties involved.

The knowledge we gather will help us create models that allow food safety officials worldwide to confirm that the food reaching consumers is genuine and hasn't been tampered with. This is especially important for making sure food remains safe and secure while it is being transported. Furthermore, our study will suggest strategies to prevent any intentional harm to food throughout its journey, ensuring its safety and security during transit.

You will complete a single online survey which is divided into three separate parts. The questions are related to food security concerns during transport. The total time dedicated to completing the survey is approximately 30 minutes. Identifiable private information collected will be your name and email. We will also collect the name of the organization that employs you, and your experience with ISO standards and Food Safety in the Supply Chain. This information will only be shared with the study team. Your survey responses will not be linked to your identifiable information. Your identifiable information will be stored separately from your de-identified information on a password-protected UCF OneDrive. All data will be stored for a minimum of five years after study closure, per Florida law.

You must be a Supply Chain Professional actively engaged in the food sector, including production, manufacturing, distribution, transportation, retail, and representatives of consumer advocacy groups. We welcome members of LinkedIn groups focused on supply chain security and food safety.

Study contacts for questions about the study or to report a problem: If you have questions, concerns, or complaints: *Celso Alvarado Jr., Graduate Student, Industrial Engineering Program, College of Engineering and Computer Science, ce616754@ucf.edu* or *Dr. Luis Rabelo, Faculty Supervisor, Department of Industrial Engineering and Management Systems by email at luis.rabelo@ucf.edu*

IRB contact about your rights in this study or to report a complaint: If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or have concerns about the conduct of this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board (IRB), University of Central Florida, Office of Research, 12201 Research Parkway, Suite 501, Orlando, FL 32826-3246 or by telephone at (407) 823-2901 or email irb@ucf.edu.

UCF HRP-254 Form v.1/31/2023

1. Before proceeding to complete the survey, please confirm that you have reviewed the HRP-254 document and provide your consent to participate by checking Yes or No below:

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Project Background

Food defense research is geared toward safeguarding the food supply chain against various threats, including tampering, adulteration, theft, or contamination, during transportation from production sites to warehouses.

This particular study explores how monitoring security concerns using emerging technologies such as IoT, AI, and blockchain can impact the confidence that supply chain executives' have in food safety during delivery via trucks.

The insights gained will be instrumental in developing confidence assessment models, assisting global food safety executives in verifying the authenticity of products reaching consumers worldwide, specifically in the context of truck transportation of food.

Additionally, the study aims to propose effective strategies, safeguarding food from intentional harm during its entire journey, ensuring its security and safety during transport.

Your Expert Background

Please give us a brief description of your background.

2. What is your name?

3. Do you hold any certifications, specialized training, or formal education in food safety management or supply chain logistics?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. How many years of experience do you have in roles related to food safety within food transportation and/or warehousing?

Mark only one oval.

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5. What countries have you worked in or had a role in related to food safety, food transportation, or warehousing.

Check all that apply.

- Afghanistan
- Albania
- Algeria
- Andorra
- Angola
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Aruba
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas, The
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Brazil
- Brunei
- Bulgaria
- Burkina Faso
- Burma
- Burundi
- Cambodia
- Cameroon
- Canada
- Cape Verde
- Central African Republic
- Chad

- Chile
- China
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo, Democratic Republic of the
- Congo, Republic of the
- Costa Rica
- Cote d'Ivoire
- Croatia
- Cuba
- Curacao
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- East Timor
- Ecuador
- Egypt
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia
- Ethiopia
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- Gabon
- Gambia
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Greece
- Grenada
- Guatemala
- Guinea
- Guinea-Bissau
- Guyana
- Haiti

- Holy See
- Honduras
- Hong Kong
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Israel
- Italy
- Jamaica
- Japan
- Jordan
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati
- Kosovo
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyzstan
- Laos
- Latvia
- Lebanon
- Lesotho
- Liberia
- Libya
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Macau
- Macedonia
- Madagascar
- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Mauritania

- Mauritius
- Mexico
- Micronesia
- Moldova
- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Morocco
- Mozambique
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- Netherlands Antilles
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger
- Nigeria
- North Korea
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau
- Palestinian Territories
- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paraguay
- Peru
- Philippines
- Poland
- Portugal
- Qatar
- Romania
- Russia
- Rwanda
- Saint Kitts and Nevis
- Saint Lucia
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- Samoa
- San Marino

- Sao Tome and Principe
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore
- Sint Maarten
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia
- South Africa
- South Korea
- South Sudan
- Spain
- Sri Lanka
- Sudan
- Suriname
- Swaziland
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syria
- Taiwan
- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Timor-Leste
- Togo
- Tonga
- Trinidad and Tobago
- Tunisia
- Turkey
- Turkmenistan
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates
- United Kingdom
- United States (USA)

- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu
- Venezuela
- Vietnam
- Yemen
- Zambia
- Zimbabwe

6. Have you used emerging technologies (AI, IoT, Blockchain), methodologies, or standards (ISO, HACCP, etc) to ensure food safety in transportation and/or warehousing?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

7. Please provide a brief list of technologies, methods, or standards used:

Relevance and Appropriateness (RA) of the Security Concerns

This section of the survey assesses the suitability and adequacy of the identified security concerns within the context of food transportation via trucks, to validate their relevance and appropriateness. Please read each Security Concern and provide your feedback.

Security Concern 1: Seal Integrity

Seal integrity refers to the condition of the security seals, which are physical locks placed on containers or doors to prevent unauthorized access. If a seal is broken, it can be an indicator of product tampering, although this is not always the case.

8. Based on your experience, how relevant is the concern of seal integrity as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 2: Cargo Presence or Absence

Changes in product presence can signal loss or theft. Monitoring product presence helps detect losses during transit, preventing theft or unauthorized removal.

9. Based on your experience, how relevant are changes in cargo presence as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 3: Truck Location

Tracking vehicle location detects irregular activity, such as unusual routes. Monitoring the planned route ensures the truck follows the designated path, flagging deviations for investigation.

10. Based on your experience, how relevant is tracking truck location as an indicator of irregularity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 4: Truck Stops

Monitoring stops identifies unexpected halts, indicating potential issues. Tracking stops reveals deviations from the planned route, highlighting any unscheduled or suspicious stops.

11. Based on your experience, how relevant is the number of stops made by vehicles in indicating irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 5: Stop Duration

Lengthy or unusual stop durations may indicate unforeseen challenges or possible security breaches. By monitoring the duration of each stop, organizations can ensure timely transportation and respond promptly to any unexpected delays.

12. Based on your experience, how relevant is the duration of vehicle stops as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 6: Open/Closed Door Status

Door status helps prevent unauthorized access during transit. Real-time monitoring of whether vehicle doors are open or closed flags any unexpected entries or exits, reducing risks associated with tampering or theft.

- 13. Based on your experience, how relevant is the open/closed status of vehicle doors as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 7: Cabin Temperature

Maintaining optimal cabin temperatures is vital for preserving product quality, especially for perishable goods. Continuous temperature monitoring ensures products are stored under ideal conditions, preventing spoilage or damage.

- 14. Based on your experience, how relevant is cabin temperature as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 8: Cabin Humidity

Appropriate humidity levels within the cabin play a pivotal role in product preservation. Monitoring cabin humidity prevents degradation of sensitive products and ensures compliance with storage standards.

15. Based on your experience, how relevant is cabin humidity as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 9: Cabin Weight Changes

Fluctuations in cabin weight might indicate product tampering, unauthorized additions, or theft. Regular weight checks provide insights into load stability and security, ensuring the integrity of transported goods.

16. Based on your experience, how relevant are changes in cabin weight as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Security Concern 10: Driver Record of Duty Status (RODS)

Keeping accurate records of driver duty status aids in transparency and compliance with transportation regulations. Ensuring all drivers are well-rested and operate within legal timeframes helps mitigate risks associated with driver fatigue and ensures adherence to transport guidelines.

17. Based on your experience, how relevant is maintaining accurate driver records as an indicator of irregular activity that may lead to a compromised food product?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Not Very Relevant

Food Defense Performance and Monitoring

In this section, we will inquire about food defense monitoring, which involves safeguarding food from intentional contamination or tampering. It encompasses measures to protect food products, supply chains, and consumers from potential threats to safety and security.

18. **Total Shipments:** *In the past 12 months, how many shipments of food products did your organization send out, transport, or receive?*

19. **Food Defense Incidents:** Of these shipments, how many experienced food defense-related incidents?

20. **Please check the types of incidents (Check all that apply)**

Check all that apply.

- Tampering: Deliberate alteration or adulteration of food products, such as adding toxic substances or foreign objects to food items.
- Contamination: Intentional introduction of biological, chemical, or physical agents into food products that could harm consumers.
- Theft: Stealing of food products, which can lead to unauthorized distribution and sale of potentially unsafe or untraceable food items.
- Cyberattacks: Targeting food production or supply chain management systems to disrupt operations, steal sensitive data, or manipulate inventory records.
- Economic Adulteration: Intentionally mislabeling or substituting food products with inferior or cheaper ingredients for financial gain, compromising food quality and safety.
- Sabotage: Actions aimed at damaging the reputation of a food company or disrupting its operations, such as falsifying lab results or spreading false alarms about food safety.
- Espionage: Stealing proprietary or confidential information related to food production processes, formulations, or security measures.
- Counterfeiting: Producing unauthorized replicas of popular food products, often lacking quality controls and safety standards.

21. **Please list the primary method(s) your organization uses to monitor and detect these incidents.**

Use of Emerging Technologies in Transporting Food via Trucks

Below, we will explore various emerging technologies and their roles in ensuring the security of food transportation.

Internet of Things (IoT): Enables real-time tracking of the truck's location and conditions inside the truck, such as temperature and humidity.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): Analyzes data from various sensors to predict potential security breaches or optimize route efficiency.

Cloud Technology: Facilitates the storage and analysis of large volumes of data from transportation operations, accessible from anywhere.

Blockchain: Ensures the integrity of food transportation records, making them tamper-proof and transparent.

22. **Which, if any, emerging technologies does your organization utilize to address transportation security concerns? Select all that apply.** *

Check all that apply.

- Internet of Things (IoT)
- Artificial Intelligence (AI)
- Cloud Technology
- Blockchain
- None of the above
- None at all
- Other: _____

23. **Please rate the effectiveness of the emerging technologies used by your organization in managing transportation security concerns on a scale from 1 (Not Effective) to 5 (Very Effective).** *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very Effective

Impact of Using a Combination of Emerging Technologies on Food Transportation Security Confidence

This section of the survey aims to understand your confidence in the security of food transportation when different emerging technologies are implemented individually and in combination. Your insights will help identify which technologies or combinations thereof are perceived as most effective in enhancing food transport security.

Instructions:

For each statement below, please rate your confidence level in the security of food transportation under the given technology deployment scenario. Use the following scale for your ratings:

- 1 - Very Low Confidence
- 2 - Low Confidence
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - High Confidence
- 5 - Very High Confidence

24. Internet of Things (IoT)

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

25. Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

26. **Cloud Technology**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

27. **Blockchain**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

28. **Combination of two technologies:**

IoT and AI

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

29. **Combination of two technologies:**

IoT and Cloud Technology

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

30. **Combination of two technologies:**

IoT and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

31. **Combination of two technologies:**

AI and Cloud Technology

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

32. **Combination of two technologies:**

AI and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

33. **Combination of two technologies:**

AI and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

34. **Combination of two technologies:**

Cloud Technology and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

35. **Combination of three technologies:**

IoT, AI, and Cloud Technology

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

36. **Combination of three technologies:**

IoT, AI, and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

37. **Combination of three technologies:**

IoT, Cloud Technology, and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

38. **Combination of three technologies:**

AI, Cloud Technology, and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

39. **All four technologies together:**

IoT, AI, Cloud Technology, and Blockchain

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

40. Please share any additional comments on how you believe these technologies individually or in combination impact the security of food transportation.

ISO Standards Confidence Assessment

As part of our ongoing efforts to understand the impact of various security measures on the confidence in food transportation security, we are interested in your perspective on the implementation of ISO 22000 and ISO 28000 standards by trucking companies.

ISO 22000 focuses on food safety management systems, ensuring the safe handling and processing of food throughout the supply chain, while ISO 28001 addresses security management systems, specifically targeting the security of goods during transportation to prevent tampering or contamination.

Instructions:

For each statement below, please rate your confidence level using the following scale for your ratings:

- 1 - Very Low Confidence
- 2 - Low Confidence
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - High Confidence
- 5 - Very High Confidence

41. How confident are you in the security of food transportation when trucking companies implement the ISO 22000 Food Safety Management System standards?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

42. How confident are you in the security of food transportation when trucking companies implement the ISO 28000 Security Management System for the Supply Chain standards?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

43. To what extent does the implementation of both ISO 22000 and ISO 28000 standards by trucking companies increase your overall confidence in the safety and security of food transportation?

Scale:

- 1 - Not at all
- 2 - Slightly
- 3 - Moderately
- 4 - Significantly
- 5 - Extremely

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely

44. Please share any additional comments.

Integration of 4IR Technologies with ISO Standards

Given the increasing integration of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies such as IoT, AI, Blockchain, and Cloud Computing with traditional standards like ISO 22000 and ISO 28000, we seek to understand how this amalgamation influences your confidence in the security of food transportation.

45. How does the combined implementation of 4IR technologies (IoT, AI, Blockchain, Cloud Computing) and ISO standards (ISO 22000, ISO 28000) affect your confidence level in the security and safety of food transportation?

Scale:

- 1 - Very Low Confidence
- 2 - Low Confidence
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - High Confidence
- 5 - Very High Confidence

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Confidence

46. How likely do you think it is that applying ISO 22000 and ISO 28001 standards will enhance the effectiveness of IoT for real-time tracking, AI for predictive analysis, Blockchain for tamper-proof records, and Cloud Computing for data management in ensuring food transportation security?

Scale:

- 1 - Very Low Likelihood of Enhancement
- 2 - Low Likelihood of Enhancement
- 3 - Moderate Likelihood of Enhancement
- 4 - High Likelihood of Enhancement
- 5 - Very High Likelihood of Enhancement

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very High Likelihood of Enhancement

47. Please share any additional comments.

Legacy Controls

Even with the implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO standards, several legacy controls would still play a crucial role in ensuring the safety and integrity of food during truck transportation. These enduring practices and procedures complement modern technologies by providing a foundational layer of security and safety measures. Some of these legacy controls include:

Physical Inspections: Regular inspections of the cargo, trucks, and equipment to check for tampering, damage, or other signs of security breaches.

Driver Training and Protocols: Comprehensive training programs for drivers on food safety handling, emergency procedures, and security awareness. Well-informed drivers are crucial for preventing incidents and responding effectively when issues arise.

Quality Control Checks: Performing manual quality control checks at loading and unloading points to verify the condition and safety of the food products. These checks can serve as a double-check alongside automated systems.

Visual Surveillance: The use of surveillance cameras at key points like loading docks, warehouses, and parking areas to monitor and record activities for security purposes.

Physical Barriers and Locks: Utilizing fences, locks, and other physical security measures to protect cargo during stops and at warehouses.

Route Planning: Although GPS and real-time tracking offer dynamic routing capabilities, initial route planning based on known risks, traffic patterns, and weather conditions remains vital.

Communications Equipment: Despite advanced communication technologies, basic communication tools like mobile phones and radios remain essential for driver-dispatcher coordination, especially in areas with poor connectivity or in emergency situations.

Manual Record-Keeping: While digital systems offer streamlined data logging, manual records can serve as backups in case of technological failures or for cross-verification purposes.

Simple Mechanical Seals: Even with the advent of electronic seals, mechanical seals might still be used as a secondary layer of security or for certain types of cargo where high-tech solutions are not feasible.

Emergency Procedures: Written emergency response plans and protocols that drivers and staff can follow in case of accidents, security breaches, or other emergencies.

By maintaining these legacy controls alongside modern 4IR technologies and ISO standards, trucking companies can ensure a comprehensive and layered approach to food safety and security during transportation.

Effectiveness of Legacy Controls

48. Based on your experience, how effective are legacy control measures (such as physical inspections, manual record-keeping, driver training, etc.) in maintaining the safety and integrity of food during transportation?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely Effective

49. Based on your experience, how significant are legacy control measures compared to modern technologies (IoT, AI, Cloud Technology, Blockchain) in contributing to the overall security of food transportation?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Muc Equally Significant

50. Based on your experience, how does the presence of legacy control measures influence your confidence in the security of food transportation by trucking companies?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Sign Significantly Increases Confidence

51. Based on your experience, how important is the integration of legacy control measures with Industry 4.0 technologies and ISO standards in forming a comprehensive food defense strategy?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely Important

52. Based on your experience, if you had to allocate resources between enhancing legacy control measures and investing in modern technologies (IoT, AI, Blockchain) for improving food transportation security, how would you prioritize legacy controls?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Low High Priority

53. Based on your experience, in areas where modern technologies and ISO standards might not fully address security concerns, how crucial are legacy controls in filling these gaps?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very Crucial

54. Please share any additional comments.

Rate the Survey

The upcoming questions are designed to gather your feedback on the survey experience. Your ratings and comments are essential for improving the quality of future research endeavors and ensuring the effectiveness of data collection processes.

55. **Comprehensiveness:**

Based on your experience, do you believe these security concerns adequately address a wide range of potential risks in food supply chains, specifically related to transportation via trucks?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

Broad Coverage of Security Concerns

56. If not, which areas or specific concerns do you think are missing?

57. **Depth of Information:**

Based on your experience, does the survey collect sufficient information about the specific security concerns related to food transportation via trucks and their potential indicators?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

No, Yes, it is relevant and provides security information.

58. If not, which areas require more in-depth exploration, and what specific questions would you suggest adding?

59. **Potential Bias:**

Based on your experience, do you think any of the security concerns or their descriptions introduce bias or assumptions?

Mark only one oval.

0 1 2 3

No, Yes, these might introduce bias or assumptions.

60. If yes, please specify which concerns and suggest modifications to mitigate bias.

61. **Overall Feedback:**

Do you have any additional comments or suggestions regarding the security concerns and their descriptions in the survey?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

62. If yes, please provide your feedback and recommendations for improvement.

63. **Consent:**

By participating in this survey, I hereby give my consent for my responses to be used for the purposes of the study, in accordance with its privacy and data use policies.

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Thank you

Thank you very much for taking the time to participate in this study. Your input is crucial to our research.

Best regards

Celso Alvarado Jr., PhD Candidate

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Department of Industrial Engineering

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APPENDIX B IRB EXEMPTION

UNIVERSITY OF CENTRAL FLORIDA

Institutional Review Board
FWA00000351
IRB00001138, IRB00012110
Office of Research
12201 Research Parkway
Orlando, FL 32826-3246

EXEMPTION DETERMINATION

April 26, 2024

Dear Celso Alvarado:

On 4/26/2024, the IRB determined the following submission to be human subjects research that is exempt from regulation:

Type of Review:	Initial Study
Title:	Food Defense 4.0: Assessing How Innovations in Truck Security Monitoring Influence Supply Chain Confidence.
Investigator:	Celso Alvarado
IRB ID:	STUDY00006221
Funding:	None
Documents Reviewed:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HRP-251 - FORM - Faculty Advisor Scientific-Scholarly Review 01192024 (2).pdf, Category: Faculty Research Approval; • Study 6221 HRP-254 - FORM - Explanation of Research - Full Study 04052024 _TF edits.pdf, Category: Consent Form; • Study 6221 HRP-255 - FORM - Request for Exemption - Celso Alvarado - 04232024.docx, Category: IRB Protocol; • Study 6221 Invitation to Participate version 3_TF edits on 04052024 _TF edits.docx, Category: Recruitment Materials; • Study 6221 Research Communications 04232024.docx, Category: Other; • Study 6221 Survey + Form 6221 HRP 254 - 04232024.docx, Category: Survey / Questionnaire;

This determination applies only to the activities described in the IRB submission and does not apply should any changes be made. If changes are made, and there are questions about whether these changes affect the exempt status of the human research, please submit a modification request to the IRB. Guidance on submitting Modifications and Administrative Check-in is detailed in the Investigator Manual (HRP-103), which can be found by navigating to the IRB Library within the IRB system. When you have completed your research, please submit a Study Closure request so that IRB records will be accurate.

If you have any questions, please contact the UCF IRB at 407-823-2901 or irb@ucf.edu. Please include your project title and IRB number in all correspondence with this office.

Sincerely,

Tamiko Fukuda
Designated Reviewer

LIST OF REFERENCES

- Abideen, A. Z., Sundram, V. P. K., Pyeman, J., Othman, A. K., & Sorooshian, S. (2021). Food Supply Chain Transformation through Technology and Future Research Directions—A Systematic Review. *Logistics*, 5(4), 83. <https://doi.org/10.3390/logistics5040083>
- Bhat, S. A., Huang, N.-F., Sofi, I. B., & Sultan, M. (2022). Agriculture-Food Supply Chain Management Based on Blockchain and IoT: A Narrative on Enterprise Blockchain Interoperability. *Agriculture*, 12(1), 40. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12010040>
- Burgess, P., Sunmola, F., & Wertheim-Heck, S. (2022). Blockchain Enabled Quality Management in Short Food Supply Chains. *Procedia Computer Science*, 200, 904-913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.01.288>
- Buzan, T. (2008). *The Mind Map Book: Unlock Your Creativity, Boost Your Memory, Change Your Life*. BBC Active.
- CDC. (2019). Food safety. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/foodsafety/foodborne-germs.html>
- Chandan, A., John, M., & Potdar, V. (2023). Achieving UN SDGs in Food Supply Chain Using Blockchain Technology. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2109. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032109>
- Department of Homeland Security. (2021, May 13). Feature Article: Protecting Food from the Farm to Our Plates. Retrieved April 12, 2023, from <https://www.dhs.gov/science-and-technology/news/2021/05/13/feature-article-protecting-food-farm-our-plates>
- Ehsan, I., Khalid, M. I., Ricci, L., Iqbal, J., Alabrah, A., Ullah, S. S., & Alfakih, T. M. (2022). A Conceptual Model for Blockchain-Based Agriculture Food Supply Chain System. *Scientific Programming*, 2022, 7358354. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7358354>
- Fan, K., Peng, Y., Tan, X., & Li, F. (2019). Blockchain technology for smart agriculture: A systematic review. *IEEE Access*, 7, 115365-115379. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2938228>
- Fernandez-Carames, T. M., & Fraga-Lamas, P. (2018). A review on the use of blockchain for the internet of things. *IEEE Access*, 6, 32979-33001. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2842685>

Finley, R., Reid-Smith, R., Ribble, C., Popa, M., Vandermeer, M., & Aramini, J. (2008). The occurrence and anti-microbial susceptibility of Salmonellae isolated from commercially available pig ear pet treats. *Zoonoses and public health*, 55(8-10), 455–461. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1863-2378.2008.01144.x>

Food and Drug Administration. (2019). Food defense. <https://www.fda.gov/food/food-defense>

Focker, M., & van der Fels-Klerx, H. J. (2019). Economics applied to food safety. Retrieved from <https://edepot.wur.nl/536509>

Food Defense. (n.d.). Retrieved April 12, 2023, from <https://www.fda.gov/food/food-defense>

Hameed, H., Zafar, N. A., Alkhamash, E. H., & Hadjouni, M. (2022). Blockchain-Based Formal Model for Food Supply Chain Management System Using VDM-SL. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114202>

Hassani, M., Silva, E., & Yari, A. (2020). Blockchain and AI-enabled IoT-based solutions for supply chain management: A review. *IEEE Access*, 8, 22583-22597.

Hassoun, A., Kamiloglu, S., Garcia-Garcia, G., Parra-López, C., Trollman, H., Jagtap, S., Aadil, R. M., & Esatbeyoglu, T. (2023). Implementation of relevant fourth industrial revolution innovations across the supply chain of fruits and vegetables: A short update on Traceability 4.0. *Food Chemistry*, 409, 135303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2022.135303>

i-scoop.eu. (n.d.). Industry 4.0: the fourth industrial revolution. Retrieved from <https://www.i-scoop.eu/industry-4-0/>

Kagermann, H., et al. (2013). Recommendations for Implementing the Strategic Initiative INDUSTRIE 4.0: Final Report of the Industrie 4.0 Working Group. Acatech - National Academy of Science and Engineering. <https://www.din.de/blob/76902/e8cac883f42bf28536e7e8165993f1fd/recommendations-for-implementing-industry-4-0-data.pdf>

Kaur, A., Singh, G., Kukreja, V., Sharma, S., Singh, S., & Yoon, B. (2022). Adaptation of IoT with Blockchain in Food Supply Chain Management: An Analysis-Based Review in Development, Benefits and Potential Applications. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, 22(21), 8174. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22218174>

- Khan, H. H., Malik, M. N., Konečná, Z., Chofreh, A. G., Goni, F. A., & Klemeš, J. J. (2022). Blockchain technology for agricultural supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic: Benefits and cleaner solutions. *Journal of cleaner production*, 347, 131268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131268>
- Khan, S., Singh, R., Khan, S., & Nghah, A. H. (2023). Unearthing the barriers of Internet of Things adoption in food supply chain: A developing country perspective. *Green Technologies and Sustainability*, 1(2), 100023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2023.100023>
- Kumar, S., Raut, R. D., Agrawal, N., Cheikhrouhou, N., Sharma, M., & Daim, T. (2022). Integrated blockchain and internet of things in the food supply chain: Adoption barriers. *Technovation*, 118, 102589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2022.102589>
- Lasi, H., et al. (2014). Industry 4.0. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 6(4), 239-242. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271950998_Industry_40
- Liang, H., Wang, J., & Duan, Y. (2020). AI-powered food supply chain management. *Computer*, 53(6), 14-23. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2020.2980786>
- Lu, Y., Li, P., & Xu, H. (2022). A Food anti-counterfeiting traceability system based on Blockchain and Internet of Things. *Procedia Computer Science*, 199, 629-636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.01.077>
- MachineMetrics. (n.d.). Industry 4.0 Technologies. [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.machinemetrics.com/blog/industry-4-0-technologies>
- Mehannaoui, R., Mouss, K. N., & Aksa, K. (2023). IoT-based food traceability system: Architecture, technologies, applications, and future trends. *Food Control*, 145, 109409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.109409>
- Mitenius, N., Kennedy, S., & Busta, F. (2013). Food Defense. In *Food Safety Management: A Practical Guide for the Food Industry* (pp. 937-958). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-381504-0.00035-4>

- Nagarajan, S. M., Deverajan, G. G., Chatterjee, P., Alnumay, W., & Muthukumar, V. (2022). Integration of IoT based routing process for food supply chain management in sustainable smart cities. *Green Technologies and Sustainability*, 1(2), 100023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2023.100023>
- Nordhagen, S., Lee, J., Onuigbo-Chatta, N., Okoruwa, A., Monterrosa, E., Lambertini, E., & Pelto, G. H. (2022). What Is Safe and How Much Does It Matter? Food Vendors' and Consumers' Views on Food Safety in Urban Nigeria. *Foods (Basel, Switzerland)*, 11(2), 225. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11020225>
- Patel, D., Sinha, A., Bhansali, T., Usha, G., & Velliangiri, S. (2022). Blockchain in Food Supply Chain. *Procedia Computer Science*, 215, 321-330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.12.034>
- Powell, W., Foth, M., Cao, S., & Natanelov, V. (2022). Garbage in garbage out: The precarious link between IoT and Blockchain in food supply chains. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 25, 100261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jii.2021.100261>
- Ramanathan, U., Ramanathan, R., Adefisan, A., Da Costa, T., Cama-Moncunill, X., & Samriya, G. (2022). Adapting Digital Technologies to Reduce Food Waste and Improve Operational Efficiency of a Frozen Food Company-The Case of Yumchop Foods in the UK. *Sustainability*, 14(24), 16614. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416614>
- Salesforce. (2019, May 7). What is the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR)? [Blog post]. Retrieved from <https://www.salesforce.com/blog/what-is-the-fourth-industrial-revolution-4ir/>
- Sánchez, A. M., Martínez, C., & Ramos, P. (2019). Blockchain as a transparency tool in the food supply chain. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 14, 45-52.
- Schwab, K. (2016). The Fourth Industrial Revolution: What It Means, How to Respond. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/01/the-fourth-industrial-revolution-what-it-means-and-how-to-respond/>
- Sharma, R., Kamble, S., Gunasekaran, A., Kumar, V., & Kumar, A. (2020). A Systematic Literature Review on Machine Learning Applications for Sustainable Agriculture Supply Chain Performance. *Computers & Operations Research*, 119, 104926. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2020.104926>

- Singh, R., Khan, S., Dsilva, J., & Centobelli, P. (2023). Blockchain Integrated IoT for Food Supply Chain: A Grey Based Delphi-DEMATEL Approach. *Applied Sciences*, 13(2), 1079. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13021079>
- Tripathi, A.K., Krishnan, K.A., & Pandey, A.C. (2023). A Novel Blockchain and Internet of Things-Based Food Traceability System for Smart Cities. *Wireless Personal Communications*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-023-10230-9>
- Tsoukas, V., Gkogkidis, A., Kampa, A., Spathoulas, G., & Kakarountas, A. (2022). Enhancing Food Supply Chain Security through the Use of Blockchain and TinyML. *Information*, 13(5), 213. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info13050213>. USDA Economic Research Service.
- Wei, Z., Alam, T., Al Sulaie, S., Bouye, M., Deebani, W., & Song, M. (2023). An efficient IoT-based perspective view of food traceability supply chain using optimized classifier algorithm. *Information Processing & Management*, 60(3), 103275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2023.103275>
- Yadav, V.S., Singh, A.R., Raut, R.D., Mangla, S.K., Luthra, S., & Kumar, A. (2022). Exploring the application of Industry 4.0 technologies in the agricultural food supply chain: A systematic literature review. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 169, 108304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2022.108304>
- Zeng, D., Cao, Z., & Neill, D. B. (2021). Artificial intelligence-enabled public health surveillance—from local detection to global epidemic monitoring and control. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, 437–453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-821259-2.00022-3>